

Workshop Report

Indigenous rights and governance instruments in the Amazon

This document brings together the debates and reflections of the workshop participants
"Indigenous rights and governance instruments in the Amazon"

This is the Workshop Report 5 of the Project "Power of Connections: Harvesting Lessons
and Strengthening Coalitions for the Conservation of the Amazon"

June 2026

Report of the Workshop "**Indigenous rights and governance instruments in the Amazon**", held from January 26 to 29, 2026 in San Patricio, Quito, Ecuador.

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1. Pan-Amazonia
2. Indigenous rights
3. Governance
4. Public policies
5. Law implementation

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List of acronyms and abbreviations

ACTO	Amazon Cooperation Treaty Organization
AIDSESP	Interethnic Association for the Development of the Peruvian Jungle
ALADTI	Latin American Alliance of Defenders of Indigenous Territory
APA	Amerindian Peoples Association
CIPRI	Political Science and International Relations Network
CLO	Community Lands of Origin
COICA	Coordinator of Indigenous Organizations of the Amazon Basin
CONFENIAE	Confederation of Indigenous Nationalities of the Ecuadorian Amazon
COP	Conference of the Parties
DAR	Organization of Rights, Environments and Natural Resources
FPIC	Free, Prior, and Informed Consent
GIA-TIM	Autonomous Indigenous Government of the Multi-Ethnic Indigenous Territory
GTI-PIACI	PIACI International Working Group
IACHR	Inter-American Court of Human Rights
IGAC	Agustín Codazzi Geographic Institute
ILO	International Labor Organization
IPO	Indigenous Peoples' Organization
IUCN	International Union for Conservation of Nature
NGO	Non-governmental organization
PIACI	Indigenous Peoples in Isolation and Initial Contact
POC	The Power of Connections
SERNANP	National Service of Natural Areas Protected by the State, Peru
SIGETI	Information System for Indigenous Territorial Management
SPDA	Peruvian Society of Environmental Law
TCD	Tropical Conservation and Development Program
TIM	Multiethnic Indigenous Territory
UF	University of Florida
UNFCCC	United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change
USA	United States of America
ZTI	Zero Tolerance Initiative

PRESENTATION

Between January 26 and 29, 2026, in Quito, Ecuador, representatives of local communities and Indigenous groups, human rights and environmental non-governmental organizations (NGOs), government entities, the private sector, and research institutions met to attend the workshop entitled "Indigenous Rights and Governance Instruments in the Amazon". This document constitutes a record of the ideas, experiences and reflections that were expressed in that space on the application of the law and public policies for the protection of Indigenous Peoples and conservation in the Amazon.

The workshop was held within the framework of the project *The Power of Connections: Harvesting Lessons and Strengthening Coalitions for the Conservation of the Amazon* (hereafter POC), an initiative of the Tropical Conservation and Development Program (TCD) of the University of Florida (UF), in collaboration with the Political Science and International Relations Network (CIPRI). and with the financial support of the Gordon and Betty Moore Foundation.

This project is based on the premise that the Amazon, one of the most biodiverse and relevant ecosystems on the planet, is deeply connected to global social, political, and economic systems. In this way, changes in international policies, priorities in the investment of economic resources, or consumption patterns in other regions of the world directly affect Amazonian peoples and territories. Therefore, the central proposal of the project is to promote collective learning processes and strengthen coalitions and collaboration networks between Pan-Amazonian countries, connecting academic, ancestral, and local knowledge.

The project recognizes that effective conservation of the Amazon can only be achieved with the Amazonian people and not in spite of them. Thus, the knowledge, practices, and ways of life developed by Indigenous Peoples, traditional communities, and local organizations offer innovative and replicable solutions of value to sustainability challenges.

This project began in January 2025 and ends in September 2026 and includes an international conference in Gainesville (USA) in February 2026 with the participation of thematic leaders and representatives of partner organizations. During this period, five thematic workshops have been held in different countries of the Amazon:

1. Sociobioeconomies and Conservation Finance (Brazil, May 2025)
2. Transforming institutions to empower the next generation of conservation leaders (Bolivia, July 2025)
3. Collaborative Management focused on Indigenous Peoples and local communities (Brazil, September 2025)
4. Innovations in the research process (Peru, December 2025)
5. Indigenous rights and governance instruments (Ecuador, January 2025)

For this fifth and final workshop, thematic presentations, group discussions, and participatory exercises were combined, inviting participants to reflect on the potential that the use of the law and various governance instruments can have for the protection of Indigenous Peoples living in the Amazon, while promoting basin conservation. For 3.5 days, participants shared

their methodological approaches, knowledge and strategies, questioning in an empathetic and constructive way, how their practices strengthen collaboration between academia, Indigenous Peoples and decision-makers, and generate social, political and environmental impacts at different scales. The workshop also included spaces for systematization of learning, analysis of specific cases, and planning of next steps.

This report presents the key moments, and the most relevant activities and topics addressed during the workshop, as documented by the University of Florida team. The intention is that these contributions serve to strengthen the positive impacts that governance instruments have had for the protection of life, territories, and rights in the Amazon.

Figure 1. Workshop participants

WORKSHOP ORGANIZATION PROCESS

This workshop, like the other four thematic workshops of the POC project, was the result of collaboration between the thematic leaders and the University of Florida (UF) team. The thematic leaders were selected several months in advance for their extensive experience in the Amazon and in the specific theme of the workshop. Thereafter, through weekly meetings, they and the UF team shaped the event: first jointly defining the objectives and then drawing up the list of participants, selected according to the relevance of their knowledge, experience, and area of action.

A few months before the workshop, the facilitation team was also formed, led by two people: the facilitator of the UF team and an external facilitator from an Amazonian country, the latter also identified by the workshop organizing team. With the objectives defined and the participants confirmed, this team designed the agenda, which was subsequently reviewed and validated by the entire organizing group.

During the workshop, facilitation was carried out with a flexible and participatory approach, ensuring that each participant could contribute meaningfully to the discussions. Every day, and even sometimes during the sessions, the organizing team met briefly to reflect, evaluate the development of the process and, if necessary, adjust the agenda along the way.

Finally, after the workshop, the organizing team worked on the results, which were shared with the participants for validation in a virtual meeting. This was an iterative process, which was refined and strengthened with each workshop.

Objectives and agenda of the workshop

The main objective of this workshop was to generate a space for dialogue and collective analysis about the experiences of the participants in the implementation of innovative strategies and legal instruments that have contributed to strengthening the protection of Indigenous Peoples, their self-determination, and conservation in the Amazon.

To this end, four specific objectives were defined and guided the exchange during the days of the workshop:

- To evaluate the positive impacts that governance instruments have had on the protection of life, territories, and rights in the Amazon.
- Reflect on the effectiveness of legal frameworks to promote the design and implementation of public policies focused on the protection of Indigenous Peoples' rights in the Amazon.
- Share innovative strategies that have been effective in strengthening Indigenous Peoples' agency and self-determination in the Amazon.
- Collectively outline next steps to support the strengthening of coalitions for Indigenous Peoples' rights, effective governance, and conservation of the Amazon

Table 1. Workshop agenda

Day	Central Theme	Activities
Day 1 26/01/2026	Building community	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Welcome. • Presentation of the objectives of the workshop. • Presentation of participants (who I am, where I work); a map of the Amazon is used to identify work area.
Day 2 27/01/2026 08h00 – 18h00	Initial Contextualization: Legal strategies and governance instruments for conservation	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Brief introduction by the thematic leader on the content and methodology of the workshop. • Understand the context. Use small group guiding questions to discuss the following topics: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. Interaction between Indigenous rights and conservation: How do you understand the relationship between conservation and Indigenous rights in your territory, country or area of work? 2. Innovative strategies for the effective protection of rights and governance: When you hear the term "innovative strategies", what comes to mind from your experience or work? 3. Indigenous self-determination and territorial self-governance: in plenary,

		<p>participants are asked for specific examples of both concepts.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Establish common bases. Comparative analysis exercise on the recognition of Indigenous Peoples' rights in national frameworks. <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - In groups organized by country, the incorporation of Indigenous Peoples' rights into the country's constitution and regulations is discussed. - Subsequently, the work carried out by each group in plenary is presented. - In plenary, a guided discussion is held in order to establish similarities, differences and political implications of the level of incorporation of the rights of Indigenous Peoples in the constitution, according to previously identified legal categories (autonomy, environment, participation, prior consultation, etc.). • Preparation activity to share experiences and strategies the next day. In plenary, the activity of the "Fair of Experiences" is briefly detailed.
<p>Day 3 28/01/2026 08h30 – 17h30</p>	<p>Best strategies in action: Methods, legal tools, and outcomes</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exchange of experiences and innovative legal strategies. A "Fair of Experiences" is organized guided by the question: What concrete examples of innovative strategies have resulted in effective protection of life, territories and rights in the Amazon that you would like to share? <ul style="list-style-type: none"> - In plenary, the experiences or initiatives to be presented during the "Fair of Experiences" are defined. You can work in groups or individually. - In addition, guidance is given to standardize the criteria of each presentation: scope, impact, success factors, challenges, adaptability, next steps. - Each group prepares its presentation in flipcharts and, subsequently in plenary, shares its initiative, project or experience.

Day 4 29/01/2026 08h30 – 17h00	Commitments and partnerships on the way forward	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Define lessons learned. In small groups, we discuss what we have learned from the experiences presented. In plenary we discuss what innovative idea we brought and what new idea we take away that we can apply. Identify potential products. In plenary sessions, the next collective steps are defined as a group to consolidate connections.
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Workshop participants

The workshop featured a diverse group of 21 participants who work on issues related to law and governance in the Amazon. Participants represented local communities and Indigenous groups, human rights and environmental non-governmental organizations (NGOs), government entities, the private sector, and research institutions. This group was joined by 9 people from the organizing team.

Table 2. List of participants present at the workshop

Name	Institution	Country of origin / action	Email
Antonio Matapi Yucuna	Instancia de Coordinación de los territorios indígenas del Macroterritorio Jaguares de Yurupari	Colombia	Secretariagjaguaresdelyurupari@gmail.com
Allex Mendonça	Instituto de Conservação e Desenvolvimento Sustentável da Amazônia	Brazil	allex.jom@gmail.com
Andrea Buitrago Castro	Fundación para la Conservación y el Desarrollo Sostenible- Perú	Peru	Andrea.buitrago@fcds.org.pe
Catalina Rivadeneira	ORE Foundation – Organización de apoyo legal y social	Bolivia	catariva27@gmail.com
Carolina Herrera	Instituto PanAmazónico	Colombia	carolina@ipanamazonico.org
Dário Cardoso Júnior	Transparência Internacional – Brazil	Brazil	dariocardosojr@gmail.com
Diana "Tita" Alvira	Independent consultant	Colombia	alvirareyestita@gmail.com
Diana Mejía	CIPRI	Ecuador	giomara.mejia@gmail.com
Hugo Che Piu Deza	Organización de Derecho, Ambiente y Recursos Naturales (DAR)	Peru	hchepiu@dar.org.pe
Johanna Espin	University of Florida	Ecuador	jespin@ufl.edu

Jonathan Dain	University of Florida	USA	jdain@latam.ufl.edu
Jony Michel Torres	CIPRI	Ecuador	1995torresjon17@gmail.com
Juan Carlos Semo Moye	Gobierno Indígena Autónomo del Territorio Indígena Multiétnico (GIA-TIM)	Bolivia	juancarlossemomoye@gmail.com
Juan David Varela	Gaia Amazonas Foundation	Colombia	jvarela@gaiaamazonas.org
Juana Hofman Quintero	The Amazon Conservation Team	Colombia	jhofman@actcolombia.org
Karen Kainer	University of Florida	USA	kkainer@ufl.edu
Leonardo Tamburini	ORE Foundation – Organización de apoyo legal y social	Bolivia	leotamburini67@gmail.com
Laurence Vandenburg	National Toshi Council, Guyana	Guyana	LaurenceVandenburg55@gmail.com
Luisa Fernanda Bacca	Instituto PanAmazónico	Colombia / Brazil	Luisa@ipanamazonico.org
Maria DiGiano	Gordon and Betty Moore Foundation	USA	maria.digiano@moore.org
Maria Fernanda Barahona	The Amazon Conservation Team	Colombia	barahonamf17@gmail.com
Marilin Mashinkash Utitaj	Confederación de Nacionalidades Indígenas de la Amazonía Ecuatoriana	Ecuador	marilynmarcela93@gmail.com
Nadia de Matos Barros	Independent researcher	Brazil	nadiadembarros@berkeley.edu
Pilar Useche	University of Florida	Colombia / USA	useche@ufl.edu
Rafael Martins da Silva	Federal Public Prosecutor's Office	Brazil	rafaelmartins@mpf.mp.br
Silvana Baldovino Beas	Sociedad Peruana de Derecho Ambiental (SPDA)	Peru	sbaldovino@spda.org.pe
Vanessa Luna	University of Florida	Peru	lunacelino.dv@ufl.edu
Walter Quertehuari	Amarakaeri Communal Reserve - Eca Amarakaeri	Peru	walter@amarakaeri.com
Wânia Cardoso	University of Florida	Brazil	cardoso.wania@ufl.edu
Yulissa Trigoso Zorrilla	Ikiam Flourish	Peru / Ecuador	yulissa.trigoso3@gmail.com

DAY 1: GETTING TO KNOW EACH OTHER

1. Welcome

Raúl Salgado, president of CIPRI, welcomed participants of the workshop "Indigenous Rights and Governance Instruments in the Amazon" to Ecuador, highlighting the ecological diversity of the country, its four regions, its richness in flora and fauna, as well as its environmental assets and challenges.

Subsequently, Marilyn Mashinkias and Yulissa Trigos, Indigenous representatives living in the Ecuadorian Amazon also welcomed the international participants. Marilyn extended an institutional greeting on behalf of the Confederation of Indigenous Nationalities of the Ecuadorian Amazon (CONFENIAE) and stressed the importance of holding spaces for close dialogue aimed at reflection, the construction of strategies, and the generation of synergies. These spaces strengthen the Amazon and contribute to joint work for the benefit of Indigenous Peoples and local communities in the territories where they live.

As part of the welcome, Maria DiGiano, program officer of the Moore Foundation, underlined the relevance of these spaces for the exchange of ideas and the construction of joint proposals, highlighting the potential, commitment, and experience of the participants, and inviting them to take advantage of the meeting as an opportunity for reflection and collective strengthening.

Next, Karen Kainer, professor at the University of Florida, in addition to the words of thanks, offered an introductory contextual and conceptual reflection of the Amazon. She noted that external media perspectives typically present narratives of deforestation and environmental destruction, making invisible the historical and daily role of the peoples and communities that inhabit it and have cared for it from generation to generation. She stressed that there are thousands of people who work daily for a fairer and more sustainable Amazon, facing complex challenges with creativity, intelligence, and commitment. In this sense, she affirmed that these collective struggles and achievements deserve to be made visible and communicated, recognizing the voices and actions of Indigenous Peoples and local communities, both for their ancestral knowledge and for their contribution to the general well-being and conservation of the Amazon biome.

Thus, she pointed out that this meeting constitutes a space to share and exchange ideas, experiences, challenges, and learning, as well as to strengthen networks and connections built over time. She mentioned that the POC project targets a diversity of actors linked to the Amazon, including professionals from Indigenous Peoples – both historical leaders and new generations – local communities, researchers, public officials, funders, and entrepreneurs. She explained that the project includes various activities, including postgraduate courses, five thematic workshops delivered in different Amazonian countries and a regional conference scheduled for February, aimed at integrating the learning from the different workshops.

Subsequently, Johanna Espin, thematic leader of the workshop, welcomed participants by pointing out her special interest in sharing this meeting in her country of origin and in a field

of work closely linked to her professional career. During her speech, she explained the process of preparing the event and its specific objectives, emphasizing that the workshop focuses on Indigenous rights in the Amazon, without ignoring the diversity of actors present in the territory.

Next, Vanessa Luna introduced the team in charge of the report and systematization of the contributions of the workshop and reported on the procedures for recording audio and photography, requesting informed consent of the participants.

Finally, Tita Alvira and Jon Dain, co-facilitators of the workshop, explained their role in accompanying the process of dialogue and collective learning, highlighting the importance of knowledge exchange, generation of new ideas, and the strengthening of networks between participants from different countries and backgrounds. During their comments, they pointed out that the facilitating team does not act as a specialist in all the topics addressed, but as a catalyst for the collective learning process, aimed at getting to know each other, sharing knowledge, and strengthening bonds. They indicated that each person was invited for the value of their contributions and expressed their expectation that everyone will return to their territories with significant learning and new and strengthened collaborative networks.

Figure 2. Tita Alvira, workshop facilitator

2. How are we going to connect and get to know each other?

Tita Alvira presented the first participatory exercise of the workshop, whose purpose was to demonstrate the territorial, institutional, and professional diversity of the participants, as well as the breadth of the experiences represented. Using a map of the Amazon basin, she asked each participant to write their name and indicate the places or territories in the Amazon where they currently work or carry out their activities.

Within the framework of this territorial presentation exercise, participants briefly shared their origin and areas of Amazonian work. Below is a synthesis of their interventions, not necessarily in the order in which they were developed but grouped by country or area of work.

Three people from Bolivia ensued. Juan Carlos Semo presented himself as a member of the Autonomous Indigenous Government of the Multiethnic Indigenous Territory, located between the provinces of Yacuma, Moxos, and Ballivián, in the department of Beni, Bolivia. In operation for approximately two years, this constitutes the first autonomous Indigenous territory in the department and one of the first in the Bolivian Amazon. He pointed out that Bolivia constitutionally recognizes 36 Indigenous Peoples, of which 18 are in Beni. He was followed by Leonardo Tamburini, who shared his experience of more than thirty years of work in Bolivia, noting that he has participated in processes related to the defense of Indigenous rights, the Constituent Assembly, and the consolidation of legal frameworks. He indicated that he is currently part of an organization that promotes the exercise of Indigenous rights and conceives of conservation as a tool for territorial empowerment and response to climate change in the Amazon and the Chaco. From this same institution, Catalina Rivadeneira, a biologist by training, pointed out that her work is concentrated in the Amazon region of southern Bolivia, particularly in Beni, supporting Indigenous governance processes linked to sustainability and forest conservation.

As for the participants from Brazil, Wânia Cardoso said that she is currently pursuing doctoral studies at the University of Florida. She was followed by Rafael Martins, who works as a prosecutor in the Brazilian Amazonian state of Pará, while Dário Cardoso shared his professional link with the Amazon territory and his work at Transparency International. Subsequently, Nadia de Matos pointed out that she works on projects aimed at strengthening Indigenous advocacy together with Indigenous organizations.

From Colombia, Antonio Matapi shared that he is part of the Indigenous Council of the Jaguares de Yurupari macro-territory located in an area near the Caquetá River, and which was recently formalized as a territorial entity. Also from Colombia, Juana Hofman presented herself as co-director of the organization The Amazon Conservation Team, based in the United States and present in countries such as Costa Rica, Colombia, Brazil, Suriname, and others. She explained that her work focuses mainly on Indigenous Peoples in isolation and/or in phases of initial contact, as well as on issues related to land and health. From this same organization, María Fernanda Barahona works on integration strategies related to Indigenous Peoples in isolation and initial contact, especially in the border areas between Colombia and Peru, where some of the peoples in confirmed isolation are located.

From Ecuador, Marilin Mashinkias indicated that she is part of the CONFENIAE that brings together more than 1,500 communities and 11 nationalities. She belongs to the Shuar nationality and explained that her work is aimed at territorial strengthening, the promotion of bio-entrepreneurship – especially led by women – and the mainstreaming of a gender approach and environmental and social safeguards, with an emphasis on Indigenous youth and governance. Subsequently, Yulisa Trigos, co-founder of Ikiam Flourish, pointed out that she develops her work in Shuar territory, promoting articulation between innovation, technology, traditional knowledge, and Indigenous economies. She indicated that the initiative has a pilot ecological reserve that is in the process of expansion and replication.

The Ecuadorians responsible for recording and systematizing workshop activities and discussions were presented next. Jony Torres, of the Chachi nationality, explained that his work focuses on the province of Esmeraldas where several Indigenous nationalities coexist and indicated that he is currently carrying out doctoral studies focused on territory, identity, mobility, and youth. Diana Mejía pointed out that she works in training on security issues in Ecuador, with emphasis on the problems associated with crime in the northern region of the country.

Laurence Vandenburg was the sole participant from Guyana and presented himself as a young Indigenous leader from a country where there are 254 Indigenous communities distributed in 10 administrative regions. From Peru, Silvana Baldovino pointed out that she develops her work in the Peruvian Amazon on issues related to institutionality, highlighting her work in the Madre de Dios region. Then, Walter Quertehuari mentioned that he is an indigenous leader currently involved in the management of the Reserva Comunal Amarakaeri – Eca Amarakaeri. Lastly, Hugo Che Piu, a lawyer from the organization DAR (Right, Environment and Natural Resources) also mentioned their work in the Peruvian Amazon, in particular related to the defense of rights of native communities.

Other participants indicated that their work is carried out in different territories of the Amazon with a more regional approach. Among them, Maria DiGiano mentioned her work in the Brazilian Amazon, as well as her link with the Moore Foundation and with processes to support its regional partners. Andrea Buitrago of the Foundation for Conservation and Sustainable Development (FCDS) pointed out that she works in the Peruvian Amazon, especially in Madre de Dios, but that her organization has been developing a regional approach since 2020 articulated between Peru, Colombia and Ecuador. Similarly, Gabriel Quijandría, IUCN national director for South America, explained that his organization works under an integral Amazon basin logic, developing projects in various countries in the region, including Peru, Ecuador, Colombia, Brazil and Bolivia.

Finally, the representatives of the academic and organizing team, Karen Kainer, Jon Dain, Vanessa Luna, Pilar Useche and Johanna Espín, thematic leader of the workshop with experience of working in Ecuador and Peru, pointed out their work trajectory in the Amazon, highlighting their role in the "Power of Connections" project, of which this workshop constitutes the fifth meeting. Pilar Useche highlighted her current position as Interim Director of UF's Tropical Conservation and Development (TCD) program and noted her work as an

DAY 2: CONTEXTUALIZATION OF LEGAL STRATEGIES AND GOVERNANCE INSTRUMENTS FOR CONSERVATION IN THE AMAZON

1. Understanding the context

Day 2 of the workshop began with a welcome from Tita, who highlighted the meeting as a space to deepen collective work, strengthen alliances, and generate new articulations between the participants. She presented the agenda of the day, aimed at building a common understanding on the relationship between conservation and Indigenous rights, innovative strategies, self-determination, and territorial governance, in addition to the analysis of national legal frameworks and a fair to exchange experiences on the subsequent day.

Participants who were not present on Day 1 were introduced as was the simultaneous translation team contracted to facilitate comfortable discussions in preferred participant languages of Spanish, English, or Portuguese. The importance of spaces for coexistence and informal exchange to strengthen relationships and networking was also reemphasized.

In plenary, participant expectations expressed in the preparatory virtual meeting were addressed, highlighting the need to build lasting alliances, promote significant learning, exchange innovative experiences, reflect on the political, social and economic challenges of the Amazon, and on the lessons learned from both accomplishments and difficulties.

Figure 4. Workshop participants at the beginning of the day

In this space for collective dialogue, participants expressed the need to critically analyze the processes of conservation, governance, and defense of rights in the Amazon. Hugo Piu stressed the importance of learning not only from successful experiences, but also from those initiatives that did not achieve expected results, stressing that failures offer fundamental lessons to strengthen future strategies. In the same vein, Juana Hofman emphasized the need to recognize the difficulties, frustrations, and crises currently faced by Indigenous Peoples, civil society, and democratic systems in the region, noting that collective thinking and solidarity are key to continue building alternatives.

For her part, Silvana proposed incorporating into the debate the regional political context and the setbacks that affect civil society, collective rights, and environmental agendas in different Amazonian countries. Leonardo highlighted the weakening of environmental institutions and the need to build new narratives that link conservation with the well-being of communities and Indigenous Peoples, as well as to open discussions on sustainable development models in the region.

Various comments reinforced the centrality of Indigenous Peoples in any territorial protection strategy. Walter insisted on the importance of emergent workshop alliances and actions being developed in direct coordination with Indigenous Peoples and responding to their territorial realities and collective rights. Juan David also raised the need to critically analyze the scope and limits of legal frameworks and fundamental and collective rights as tools for transformation.

In response to the reflections raised, Tita recalled that although the workshop emphasizes the positive aspects and the identification of valuable experiences, the process recognizes that progress has been accompanied by difficulties and failures, from which significant learning has been extracted and that this is part of the path traveled. She also emphasized the importance of not centralizing work frustrations, but of reorienting the challenges towards the construction of innovations with transformative potential, capable of strengthening territorial processes and actions in defense of collective rights.

Subsequently, Jon provided a space to agree on principles of coexistence and participation during the workshop. Agreed upon behaviors included respect of schedules, the promotion of equitable participation, mutual care in discussions, and the confidentiality of certain sensitive exchanges.

Finally, Tita highlighted the general objectives of the workshop to evaluate the impacts of governance instruments on the protection of life, territories, and rights in the Amazon; to reflect on the effectiveness of legal frameworks; to share innovative strategies to strengthen Indigenous self-determination; and to define next steps to consolidate networks and coalitions in defense of Indigenous rights and Amazonian conservation.

2. Our collective understanding

To continue the workshop work, Johanna Espín presented a framework of analysis that could contribute to the reflections to be developed later. She indicated that one of the main axes would be an analysis of innovative strategies, which could be linked both to legal frameworks – including laws, regulations and standards – and to public policies created for the protection of rights. The purpose of this analytical framework is to highlight that laws only make sense when they are translated into concrete practices and effective protection mechanisms in the territories. She also pointed out that regulatory processes are not linear, but are intersected by advances, tensions, crises, and accumulated learning.

A plenary space for reflection then focused on the need to protect the normative systems of Indigenous Peoples. Juana proposed incorporating legal pluralism as a transversal axis of the workshop, pointing out that laws must be understood not only from state law, but also from rights themselves - the rights of origin and other systems of knowledge and territorial regulation. In the same vein, Hugo highlighted the coexistence of multiple regulatory systems in the territories, many times more effective than state regulations, and stressed that these respond to specific cultural contexts and worldviews, so they cannot be analyzed or replicated mechanically. Leonardo added that laws and policies should be seen as tools, while the focus of the analysis should be on the territorial actors that promote, implement, and defend them.

These interventions broadened the discussion to the ecological, cultural and historical dimensions of territorial governance. Andrea pointed out the existence of another order of the territory and ecosystems that precedes state regulations and sustains the forms of Indigenous organization. Walter recalled a comprehensive vision of the territory as a living space linked to culture, food, medicine, and spirituality. He questioned the limitations of prior consultation to guarantee a real impact. Maria complemented by pointing out that legal norms and systems are historical and contextual constructions, shaped by specific political and social processes.

For laws to fulfill their function to guarantee rights, they have to be applied in practice
– Johanna Espín

Towards the end of the plenary discussion, Antonio pointed out the need to clarify the use of the term "law", highlighting that decisions adopted in the territories also constitute legitimate norms of governance, with their own full value, and which dialogue on equal terms with state regulatory frameworks.

Finally, Tita began the group work aimed at deepening shared understanding. This exercise would be developed in groups organized by country to discuss a first question: *"How do you understand the relationship between conservation and the rights of Indigenous Peoples in their territory, country and area of work?"*.

2.1. How do you understand the relationship between conservation and the rights of Indigenous Peoples in their territory, country and area of work?

Colombia

Antonio and María Fernanda highlighted the close relationship between territory, rights, and Indigenous governance in conservation processes, pointing out that this must be understood from a comprehensive and rights-based perspective, based on Indigenous Peoples' own systems of knowledge, norms, and forms of government.

Figure 5. Workshop participants during group exercise (Colombia Group)

The group concluded that conservation and rights are interdependent since the protection of forests and ecosystems depends on the guarantee of territorial rights and ancestral practices of care for the territory. It was highlighted that Indigenous Peoples continue to conserve their territories even without full state recognition, although the need to strengthen legal and institutional frameworks to consolidate these processes was emphasized.

Likewise, tensions with conventional conservation approaches were identified, especially in the presence of external actors, economic interests, and conflicts between normative and epistemological systems. The importance of adapting existing institutions to guarantee effective participation of Indigenous Peoples in territorial governance, rather than creating new structures, was underlined. Finally, the diversity of realities in the Amazon and the need to articulate rights, knowledge, and coordination between actors in the face of the different territorial pressures was recognized.

Peru

Peru's working group analyzed the relationship between conservation and Indigenous rights as a dynamic process traversed by historical tensions between the state, Indigenous Peoples, and extractive interests. The overlap of protected areas, mining, oil, and forestry concessions on ancestral territories was highlighted because it has generated socio-environmental conflicts and affected the integrity of Indigenous territories.

Experiences of collaborative management were noted but emphasized that co-management does not fully guarantee the recognition or effective participation of Indigenous Peoples in decision-making, demonstrating an asymmetry between conservation advances and the recognition of territorial rights. In this framework, the imposed conservation models and narratives that reduce Indigenous Peoples to the role of "guardians" of nature were questioned, underlining that conservation is part of an integral relationship with the territory.

Finally, the Peru group participants raised the need to strengthen rights-based conservation approaches, which recognize Indigenous Peoples as central political and territorial actors and integrate worldviews, autonomy, and governance in ecosystem management.

Brazil

The Brazil group analyzed the relationship between conservation and Indigenous Peoples' rights, highlighting that their recognition is directly linked to the effective territorial protection. They stressed that Indigenous ways of life contribute to conservation, with scientific evidence revealing better environmental outcomes in Indigenous territories, as in the case of the Apyterewa Indigenous Land.

However, a gap was identified between legal recognition of rights and rights implementation as reflected in invasions, violence, and institutional weaknesses. Discourses that assign Indigenous Peoples the exclusive responsibility of "protecting the planet" were also questioned, without considering the main structural causes of environmental degradation.

Finally, the group underscored the need to strengthen effective participation in decision-making, incorporate gender approaches, and promote non-colonial intercultural dialogues that recognize the internal diversity of Indigenous Peoples and avoid unequal relations with external actors.

Bolivia and Ecuador

The group from Bolivia and Ecuador addressed the relationship between conservation and Indigenous Peoples' rights from a comprehensive perspective, highlighting that territory cannot be understood as a resource, but as a living space in which material, cultural, spiritual, and political dimensions are articulated. In this sense, conservation was understood not only

as a tool for environmental protection, but also to guarantee the continuity of Indigenous ways of life within their territories.

The role of collective rights and Indigenous women in territorial governance also was highlighted. Recognition of collective rights has made it possible to broaden the framework of conservation, incorporating previously invisible dimensions such as spirituality, culture, and Indigenous forms of governance and territorial use and regulation that are built on ancestral knowledge and articulated in some cases with state institutions.

Thus, it was emphasized that conservation has become a political tool for Indigenous Peoples, as it allows strengthening territorial governance, confronting extractive pressures, and disputing development models that fragment territories. For this reason, conservation and rights cannot be understood separately, but as interdependent dimensions of the same struggle for life and self-determination.

Indigenous Peoples exist because of their territory and vice versa; territories exist because of Indigenous Peoples. This premise is fundamental and is what largely sustains the rights achieved by Indigenous Peoples – Leonardo Tamburini

Leonardo also pointed out that conservation has made it possible to broaden the understanding of the Amazon as a biome inhabited and sustained by Indigenous Peoples. He also warned about the current crisis of Indigenous organizations in the region that are affected by debilitating processes and state interventions. He raised the need to strengthen the governance capacity of Indigenous Peoples given scenarios of high extractive pressure and climate change.

Figure 6. Workshop participant during group exercise (Bolivia and Ecuador Group)

Marilin emphasized that the relationship between conservation and rights must be understood in a comprehensive way, incorporating dimensions such as food sovereignty, education, health, and cultural identity, while overcoming the separation between nature and human beings. In some contexts, such as Ecuador's, this vision is also expressed in the constitutional recognition of the rights of nature.

Overall, the group concluded that conservation, from an Indigenous perspective, is inseparable from collective rights and continuity of life in the territory, constituting both a practice of care and a political tool for territorial affirmation and governance.

Guyana

The Guyana group presented the relationship between conservation and Indigenous Peoples' rights as complex and intersected by tensions between environmental protection, territorial rights, and extractive pressures. Although some conservation initiatives restrict traditional practices such as fishing, hunting or logging, this group stressed that conservation is not viable without the active participation of Indigenous Peoples who have historically maintained practices of responsible forest use.

Figure 7. Workshop participant during group exercise (Guyana Group)

They also highlighted positive articulations between Indigenous organizations and conservation entities, such as the Amerindian Peoples Association (APA) and Conservation International. Jointly, they have confronted threats such as illegal mining and river pollution, while strengthening long-term community planning.

The group also identified the incomplete status of Indigenous land titling as a main challenge. Even in titled territories, control of the subsoil typically remains in State hands, generating tensions and negative impacts in Indigenous territories faced with mining and forestry concessions.

Nonetheless, while the conservation agenda does not always fully coincide with the Indigenous community priorities, in some cases it does contribute to territorial defense against illegal activities. While these processes often prompt cultural transformations, especially the loss of traditional languages and practices, some “conservation” projects have incorporated cultural and linguistic revitalization initiatives.

Finally, the group highlighted that community sustainability plans have strengthened local autonomy, cultural transmission, and community planning. However, it was insisted that problems related to land tenure and extractive pressure continue to shape the relationship between conservation and Indigenous rights in Guyana.

Reflection in plenary

Following presentations by country group, a plenary space was opened to share reflections on the exercise that allowed them to travel through different geographies and realities. The facilitator proposed a collective feedback space to identify common learning and differences between countries, asking: What did you hear? What did you learn? What is different?

Figure 8. Workshop participants during plenary discussion

Catalina Rivadeneira highlighted that, despite differences between national contexts, regional similarities exist in the way Indigenous Peoples conceive of their relationship with territory and conservation. From her experience, understanding the relationship between Indigenous rights and biodiversity conservation has been a continuous learning process. "I come from the field of conservation; I am still assimilating and trying to understand how we can unite this relationship between the rights of a people and the conservation of biodiversity." She stressed the importance of analyzing conservation in all its complexity, not only as a tool to strengthen rights, but also understanding what conservation implies beyond the human sphere as a condition for the continuity of all life.

For his part, Juan Carlos Semo shared a reflection from his territorial experience in Bolivia, highlighting that conservation should be understood as an instrument for the management and defense of life in Indigenous territories. Following a lengthy struggle to recognize land rights, he stated that his territory went from being a space concessioned to logging companies to a titled Indigenous territory. He also explained that obtaining the title opened a new stage of political construction that resulted in the demand for Indigenous autonomy and the formation of their own government. He pointed out that "the issue of conservation is an instrument, because territories do not take care of themselves," emphasizing the role of territory in the planning and protection of Indigenous ways of life. As a corroborating concrete experience that came out of their territorial governance exercise, Juan Carlos pointed to the creation of the Loma Santa conservation area that is within the GIA-TIM (Autonomous Indigenous Government of the Multiethnic Indigenous Territory), and officially recognized at the national level.

Marilin presented the experience of working with the Shuar nationality in Ecuador, where they identified challenges linked to over hunting in some communities. She stressed that solutions were built collectively, through community dialogue and participation of different social actors, including women, wise community members, grandparents, and young people. She stressed that these conservation agreements did not arise from external forces, but from Indigenous norms and internal organizational structures. These were later incorporated into Shuar internal statutes. She also highlighted the intergenerational dimension of the process that strengthened transmission of knowledge and practices of care for the territory. Finally, she pointed out that these initial experiences could be replicated in other organizations, reaffirming a common regional vision "as Amazonians we share the same mission to protect."

In closing, Tita recalled the logistical aspects of the day and gave way to a second moment of work to reflect on innovative strategies.

2.2. When you hear the term "innovative strategies", what ideas or experiences from your work or career come to mind?

Group 1: Antonio, Leonardo, Silvana, Maria, Karen

Group 1 reflected on the concept of "innovative strategies", agreeing that innovation does not necessarily imply creating new models, but rather could involve re-signifying and reappropriating existing tools from Indigenous logics. In this sense, the creative use of

conservation instruments to strengthen autonomy and territorial defense was highlighted as a central innovation.

The creation of Indigenous conservation areas directly managed by Indigenous governments was highlighted as a relevant experience, especially in Bolivia, where these conservation prototypes are built from their own systems of governance, communal control, and traditional authority. The group noted that these experiences challenge traditional models of conservation based on mistrust of Indigenous self-governance.

At the regional level, a number of innovative experiences were identified. In Peru, communal reserves were mentioned as mechanisms of collaborative (or co-) management between the State and Indigenous Peoples, as well as land titling as a strategic tool in the face of extractive pressures. In Colombia, the recognition of Indigenous Territorial Entities (ITE) is the result of more than three decades of political struggle, in addition to Decree 488 and the construction of macro-territories as strategies of articulation and advocacy for territorial defense.

The group agreed that these experiences form a continuum of governance that ranges from state management and co-management to forms of direct management by Indigenous governments, which is considered the most transformative. Likewise, the cross-border dimension of these strategies and the need to strengthen regional articulations in the face of shared problems such as illegal mining and environmental degradation were highlighted as innovative.

Figure 9. Workshop participant during presentation of their group work

Finally, it was emphasized that innovation also includes political and financial dimensions, especially in relation to the sustainability of Indigenous autonomy and governance. Antonio synthesized these elements by pointing out that the strategies identified are innovative precisely because they arise from the Indigenous Peoples themselves and not from the central governments. He highlighted as common axes the following: autonomy in territorial decision-making, direct management or co-management of conservation areas, the construction of intercultural agreements, and the need to strengthen financing mechanisms and regional pacts to consolidate Indigenous governance in the Amazon.

Group 2: Yulissa, Luisa, Mafer, Andrea, Johanna

Group 2 pointed out that innovation cannot be reduced to technology or the creation of new tools, but implies transformations in the ways of thinking, relating, and building solutions. They proposed a critical reflection on the concept of innovative strategies, pointing out that these are usually presented as responses to long-standing problems, often associated with technical or instrumental solutions. However, innovation cannot be limited to the incorporation of new tools but implies a deeper transformation in the ways of thinking and approaching problems, promoting more comprehensive and complex approaches that overcome fragmented visions.

Figure 10. Diagram developed by the members of the group

From the perspective of Indigenous Peoples, the group questioned the notion of "adaptation" to external initiatives, noting that it reproduces asymmetrical relationships. In contrast, they proposed understanding innovation as a process that arises from Indigenous contexts to build autonomous solutions from their territorial and cultural realities.

The group also addressed the current tensions between conservation, rights, and economic needs, noting that peoples face increasing material pressures that demand creative responses. It was emphasized that innovation also implies questioning established discourses and opening spaces for dialogue with historically excluded actors, even those with whom one has not traditionally interacted, such as public forces or economic actors. In this sense, it was proposed that innovating can mean "contradicting an idea that has been repeated many times" and rethinking the frameworks from which conservation and rights are understood.

Another important axis was the strategic use of language for political advocacy. Innovation also consists of translating territorial demands into languages understandable by the State and other power actors, especially economic language, to strengthen territorial defense from new discursive tools.

An additional needed innovation is to harmonize conservation policies with Indigenous rights, overcoming the fragmentation between both approaches and facing head on the imposition of protected areas that do not integrate full recognition of Indigenous territoriality.

Another central theme was the need to build sustainable local economies. Particularly in the face of illegal economies, innovation is needed to strengthen territorial management and collaboration between actors by articulating Indigenous, scientific, technical, and economic knowledge.

In the group's presentation, Yulissa synthesized these reflections by pointing out that Indigenous Peoples have historically been placed in a logic of adaptation to external proposals, without considering their own knowledge. She highlighted the importance of discussing issues such as money and the strategic use of legal tools so that Indigenous Peoples can reappropriate legal norms and tools for their own defense.

It's time to innovate from the inside out, from the perspective of Indigenous Peoples outwards – Yulissa Trigoso

Luisa emphasized the importance of openness and flexibility in the processes of accompaniment, questioning the conceptual "boxes" from which reality is interpreted. In addition, she pointed out that innovations have different rhythms, some require immediate responses and others longer processes of collective construction and warned that factors such as development models can limit their implementation.

Finally, the group agreed that innovation implies building bridges between diverse knowledge systems, languages, and actors, with the aim of strengthening interculturality as a real process of joint construction with an impact on public policies.

Group 3: Marilin, Walter, Juan David, Catalina, Darío, Vanessa

This group agreed that the concept of "innovative strategies" cannot be limited to technology or the creation of entirely new solutions. On the contrary, it was emphasized that innovation

implies transformations in the forms of organization, in the institutions, and in the relations between the State and Indigenous Peoples, broadening their understanding to the fields of knowledge, people and modes of collective organization.

Antonio added that innovation should also be understood as a process of reorganization of knowledge and human capacities in specific territorial contexts: "We cannot only think of innovation in terms of technology, we also have to think of innovation in terms of knowledge and people."

From this perspective, the group proposed shifting the emphasis from the idea of innovation to that of institutional adequacy, understood as the transformation of state frameworks to recognize and guarantee the functioning of Indigenous knowledge and governance systems under conditions of greater equality. It was highlighted that these systems have existed historically since before the formation of national states, so the main challenge is not to create them, but to adapt state structures to reduce asymmetrical relations.

During the discussion, experiences of conservation areas directly managed by Indigenous governments were shared, where territorial governance is articulated with daily practices of community use and surveillance. Marilyn exemplified this logic by pointing out that "the protected area is created by them and managed by them, under their own forms of organization."

Likewise, experiences of co-management and shared governance in Peru were presented, such as communal reserves, where inequalities persist in access to and control of resources, as well as cases of conservation areas promoted by Indigenous territorial governments in Bolivia. Colombia highlights included recognition of Indigenous territorial entities and other frameworks aimed at strengthening Indigenous autonomy and governance, the result of long processes of political struggle. Overall, the group identified a continuum of governance models ranging from state management to forms of direct Indigenous management, which was considered the most transformative.

Finally, examples of strategies promoted by Indigenous organizations that integrate conservation, economy, education, and organizational strengthening were incorporated, including territorial monitoring, community tourism, non-formal education, and capacity building of women and youth. The group concluded that the so-called "innovative strategies" are based, to a large extent, on the revaluation of Indigenous knowledge systems and on the adaptation of state structures to move towards more equitable relations in territorial management.

In summary, the group concluded that what are often referred to as "innovative strategies" are largely based on the revaluation of Indigenous knowledge systems and the transformation of state structures to enable their effective functioning. Rather than the creation of new solutions, emphasis was placed on the need to adapt existing institutional frameworks to move towards more equitable relations between the State and Indigenous Peoples in territorial management.

Group 4: Juan Carlos, Juana, Alex, Rafael, Wânia

This group also questioned the concept of "innovative strategies," noting that it should not be understood as the creation of entirely new solutions, but as the ability to recognize and articulate diverse knowledge—especially that of Indigenous Peoples—in legal, political, and territorial management processes. In this framework, innovation arises from the dialogue of knowledge and collective construction, rather than inventing structures from scratch.

From a legal standpoint, a critique of the “innovation” term itself was raised. Listening to Indigenous Peoples and recognizing other normative systems should not be considered an innovation, but a historical debt of Western law. In this sense, the need to move towards approaches of legal pluralism and to redefine the role of legal professionals as companions and bridges between knowledge systems, and not as actors that impose frameworks of interpretation, was underlined.

The group also emphasized that strategies are effective when they are based on active listening and recognition of community decisions. One participant stressed that solutions built without dialogue with communities often fail because the protagonists do not know territorial dynamics. Juana pointed out that the group understood innovation as a process of "renewing from within", highlighting listening as a central practice of active recognition of other knowledge systems, especially in the legal field. Overall, it was agreed that innovation implies listening, recognizing and building together to strengthen the autonomy and decision-making capacity of Indigenous Peoples.

For his part, Juan Carlos presented the case of the Multiethnic Indigenous Territory (TIM) in Bolivia. In this case, he pointed out that Indigenous autonomy made it possible to move towards their own forms of government and territorial administration, including election of authorities under their own rules. Juan Carlos explained that the declaration of the conservation area within the TIM allowed the Indigenous government to exercise direct control over the territory, administer it according to its own rules, and strengthen its legal recognition at the national level. This process and result constituted a key tool to prevent territorial loss. In this sense, he pointed out that this designation functioned as a protection mechanism against oil threats and legal disputes, by incorporating additional arguments in processes before the Agro-environmental Tribunal.

The creation of an Indigenous conservation area, "Loma Santa", was used as a legal and political strategy for territorial defense against extractive concessions, dispossession processes, and lawsuits before judicial entities (...) There was a historical process of formation, from original [state-designated] forest concessions to recognition as Indigenous territory, but this process was marked by conflicts with logging companies, state decisions, and full of territorial struggles, including the Indigenous March of 1990 and many stages of partial titling until consolidation in 2018 – Juan Carlos Semo

Finally, Juan Carlos highlighted the implementation of its own territorial surveillance system through community forest rangers, which integrates traditional practices and environmental monitoring to confront illegal activities such as logging and unauthorized fishing. This strategy also responds to needed local capacity strengthening to manage and defend the territory from the communities themselves, and as a tactic to protect strategic areas of the territory, especially areas of river headwaters under external pressure.

Group 5: Hugo, Pilar, Lawrence, Nadia

This group approached innovative strategies as a set of practices that articulate community planning, Indigenous self-governance, climate financing, regulatory recognition, and legal instruments for territorial defense. It was emphasized that these strategies are not only new technical tools, but also situated processes that emerge from territorial realities and the capacity of Indigenous Peoples to influence different levels of governance.

From the Guayana experience, the role of community plans as key instruments to guide local development was highlighted, allowing communities to define their own priorities in areas such as education, health, language, and ways of life. The relationship between conservation and climate finance was also highlighted, noting that resources derived from low-carbon development strategies are returned to Indigenous communities in recognition of historical forest protection and carbon storage.

From Brazil, an experience focused on strengthening legal capacities through a training program for Indigenous lawyers to exchange knowledge and strategic litigation in defense of lands and collective rights. The importance of having permanent legal teams within Indigenous organizations was underlined to avoid only reactive responses to conflicts.

The group also addressed the regulatory framework as a central component of innovative strategies. In Guyana, recognition of Indigenous self-governance through the Amerindian Act of 2006 was emphasized, and the importance of Free, Prior, and Informed Consent to ensure effective participation of communities in external projects.

At the international level, efforts to position Indigenous territories as key conservation spaces through certification mechanisms and multilateral frameworks such as the Convention on Biological Diversity were mentioned. However, the group warned of the risk in instrumentalizing both Indigenous Peoples and conservation mechanisms when reducing these matters to utilitarian logics without a rights-based approach.

Finally, new legal tools were explored, such as the use of the concept of ecocide to document and prosecute large-scale environmental damages. Overall, this group organized the innovative strategies into three main axes: 1) strengthening Indigenous autonomous government, 2) recognition of Indigenous contributions to conservation, and 3) development of legal and institutional tools for territorial defense. In all cases, the diversity of national trajectories was stressed, recognizing that these strategies are configured in a situated manner, in dialogue between diverse normative, political, and cultural systems.

Final reflection by the thematic leader

Following group discussions, Johanna acknowledged that the process built a shared understanding based on viewpoint diversity of the participants. She stressed that throughout the day it was possible to identify, define, and relate concepts based on concrete examples, which have been cited in different ways – such as innovative strategies, adaptation processes, or ways of "renewing from within" – reflecting the plurality of approaches present in the workshop.

She also emphasized the number of successful experiences or significant advances presented, even in contexts marked by obstacles and tensions, underlining the role of legal frameworks and technical and legal support in these processes. She also pointed out that the purpose of the workshop is precisely to favor the exchange of learning, the projection of experiences, and the construction of networks and alliances. While not possible to delve into all cases in detail within the time available, it will be necessary to prioritize topics to be addressed in the following sessions.

Subsequently, she introduced the final activity of this first part of the workshop - a plenary exercise aimed at consolidating the collective understanding built so far. She invited participants to specify key conceptual distinctions between *self-determination* and *Indigenous self-governance*, collectively refining definitions for next workshop steps.

2.3. What is the difference between the concepts of self-determination and self-governance?

The plenary discussion prompted conceptual deepening of these two terms based on complementary participant contributions. They agreed that both terms are closely linked, although they operate at different levels of analysis and political practice.

Figure 11. Workshop participants during plenary discussion

Leonardo opened the discussion by situating self-determination as a principle of broad historical and political scope, originating in the decolonization processes promoted within the United Nations framework. He explained that this concept refers to the possibility that peoples constitute themselves as full political subjects, even beyond state borders, and that in that sense "it would ignore the national borders within which Indigenous Peoples are located." He pointed out that self-determination functions as an articulating principle of other rights, including autonomy and self-governance, establishing a hierarchical relationship in which "the relationship that exists is from gender to species; it is from self-determination that other rights are exercised." He also stressed that in the case of Indigenous Peoples, this principle is reinforced by their existence prior to State formation, which implies the recognition that these are peoples who have historically been deprived of their capacity for political decision-making over their territories and ways of life.

Luisa proposed to understand both concepts as profoundly complementary. She pointed out that self-determination is related to the possibility of deciding without coercion or external pressure on one's life, development, and territorial organization projects. Self-governance, in contrast, is expressed in the effective capacity to exercise self-government. She explained that the latter implies the existence of government structures, their own jurisdictions, and recognized territories where Indigenous Peoples can define norms, administer justice, and coordinate with other levels of government. Silvana reinforced this idea by synthesizing the relationship between the two concepts: "Self-determination refers to the right and self-governance to its practical exercise." She emphasized that one cannot exist without the other, since the law only makes sense in its concrete materialization in the form of government.

Along the same lines, Juana also incorporated a jurisdiction approach to specify the practical scope of self-governance, explaining that this is understood as the ability to define who establishes the norm and in which territory it is applied. This allows the exercise of Indigenous government in its own spaces and visualized in a concrete way. This precision grounded the concepts in operational dimensions when exercising authority and territorial administration.

Johanna closed the plenary discussion, stressing that like other terms previously debated, self-determination and self-governance are different but interdependent notions, which cannot be understood in isolation. Finally, she appreciated the collective work developed during the day and introduced the next workshop phase focused on the analysis of legal frameworks at the national level.

3. Legal advances, recognition, and guarantees of Indigenous Peoples' rights

Jon introduced the group work methodology and the thematic axes that would structure the last activity of the day designed to guide comparative reflection between countries and systematize participant experiences. The exercise was organized around seven major themes:

- 1) Land rights and land tenure
- 2) Natural resources and territorial governance

experience of the Multiethnic Indigenous Territory (TIM) and the system of Indigenous autonomies in the Plurinational State of Bolivia. It was emphasized that the starting point of the analysis is the constitutional recognition of Indigenous self-government, considered the structural basis of the territorial governance model.

Leonardo explained that Indigenous autonomies have constitutional rank equivalent to that of other levels of government, which implies an effective redistribution of competencies and jurisdictions. The system recognizes "the possibility of forming their own governments with full jurisdiction," understood as the ability to exercise justice and make decisions within the framework of administrative, political, and patrimonial competencies. This recognition also includes access to direct public financing for the execution of these competencies. Self-government, he pointed out, is expressed in a set of 82 competencies that cover areas such as health, education, roads, and cultural heritage, which are exercised through their own autonomous statutes that shape territorial management.

Indigenous autonomy in Bolivia is not only administrative, but also jurisdictional and political, incorporating executive, legislative, and judicial functions. Indigenous authorities have the capacity to legislate, regulate, and make jurisdictional decisions of justice, which places Indigenous justice on the same level as ordinary jurisdiction, with the exception of constitutional jurisdiction. This design also implies a redistribution of territorial power, given that the formation of Indigenous autonomies implies the reassignment of competencies previously exercised by municipalities and departments.

In the analysis of the TIM case, Catalina stressed that it is the first Amazonian Indigenous autonomy in Bolivia, recently constituted as an autonomous Indigenous government. One of its first normative actions was the creation of an Indigenous protected area, conceived as a strategy for territorial defense and recognition of the cultural and material relationship within the territory, especially in areas of water sources and life systems based on hunting and fishing. This process resulted in the construction of territorial planning instruments, in which traditional ecological knowledge, such as the interpretation of natural cycles associated with the moon and local climatic dynamics, are integrated as a basis for land management.

The TIM developed its own system of territorial control and surveillance, in which community members – hunters and fishermen – are recognized as community forest rangers. Unlike conventional conservation models, there is no separation between community life and environmental monitoring, rather, both roles are integrated into everyday practice. This system allows the inhabitants themselves to record and report events in the territory, articulating environmental control with local organizational structures.

In emergencies such as floods, the Indigenous government is the one who receives and distributes state aid directly, prioritizing communities and defining response mechanisms through internal assemblies. Likewise, the autonomous government directly carries out the management of infrastructure, such as roads and bridges, which contrasts with previous periods of institutional marginalization.

Leonardo illustrated the exercise of Indigenous jurisdiction through cases of territorial control in the face of external incursions, in which the Indigenous authorities have applied

sanctions, confiscations, and expulsions. This reinforces the fully operational nature of Indigenous jurisdiction in Bolivia within the framework of the plurinational State.

Finally, the group stressed that the Bolivian model is characterized by an open constitutional system, which allows for incorporation of international standards and comparative jurisprudence in the field of Indigenous rights and the rights of nature. Leonardo noted that national courts have adopted decisions inspired by rulings of other countries in the region, which has allowed, for example, to recognize rivers as subjects of rights and to declare cases of pollution as serious violations. This circulation of jurisprudence reinforces a dynamic approach to law, in which international, regional, and local decisions are articulated to strengthen the protection of Indigenous territories and their systems of life.

The Bolivian experience was presented as a model of articulation between Indigenous jurisdiction, self-government, and territorial management. Here, constitutional recognition, direct management of resources, internally controlled planning, and the openness of the legal system allow for Indigenous governance to have a high degree of autonomy, while also in constant negotiation with the plurinational state framework.

Indigenous autonomies have the three strong competencies of any government: legislative capacity, executive and patrimonial capacity, and judicial capacity. That is, they can judge and act on these three aspects. – Leonardo Tamburini

Brazil: Natural Resources and Territorial Governance / Participation and Free, Prior, and Informed Consent

The Brazil group focused its discussion on the tensions between the formal recognition of Indigenous Peoples' rights and their effective implementation, especially in relation to Free, Prior, and Informed Consent (FPIC), the land ownership regime, and the development of the carbon market.

The analysis emphasized that, although there have been recent regulatory advances, significant gaps persist in realizing rights guarantees. For example, based on an investigation into the carbon market, it was determined that these mechanisms not only involve risks of corruption, but also possible violations of rights, particularly in relation to prior consultation. For this reason, they stressed that, although FPIC is formally incorporated into the new carbon market legislation, its application has weaknesses. In many cases, compliance with the formal consultation protocol allows projects to move forward without ensuring conditions for effective participation, which limits their scope to guarantee rights. In addition, not all communities have their own technical capacities or consultation protocols, which reduces their capacity for advocacy and informed decision-making in the face of projects that affect their territories.

Rafael underlined the distance between legal recognition and the real protection of Indigenous territories. He stressed that the Brazilian State maintains an ambivalent role, since, although it should be the guarantor of territorial rights, in many cases it has been one

of the main agents of violation, especially in the context of large infrastructure projects such as hydroelectric plants.

The group also analyzed the structural limitations of the Indigenous land regime in Brazil, where ownership of the territory belongs to the federal government, while Indigenous Peoples exercise only possession and usufruct rights. This legal separation was identified as a factor that opens wide margins of interpretation for exceptions linked to concepts such as "national interest" or "national security". This has historically allowed the implementation of extractive or infrastructure projects in Indigenous territories, including large-scale projects such as the case of Belo Monte.

Despite this scenario, the group also highlighted experiences of resistance and territorial defense that have influenced state decision-making. The case of the São Luiz do Tapajós hydroelectric plant in Munduruku territory was mentioned. This project was finally canceled after Indigenous mobilization and its accompaniment by institutions such as the Federal Public Prosecutor's Office, the Public Defender's Office, and allied organizations. This case was presented as a significant example of articulation between Indigenous and institutional actors for the defense of territories against megaprojects.

Finally, the group emphasized the formal recognition of Indigenous territories is not the end point of the struggles, but only an initial stage in an ongoing process of territorial defense. Even after titling, invasions, conflicts over resources, and economic and political pressures persist, which shows that the effective guarantee of self-determination requires more robust mechanisms for the protection, implementation, and monitoring of rights.

It is provided for in the law, that is very good. But the general impression is that once companies comply with the protocol to consult communities, they can move forward with the project. There is still a fragility of how this consultation will happen and of the mechanisms to ensure that communities are heard. – Alex Mendonça

Ecuador: Natural Resources and Territorial Governance / Participation and Free, Prior, and Informed Consent / Cosmovisions and Rights of Nature

In the Ecuador group, the participants agreed that there is a recurring paradox. While the 2008 Constitution incorporates significant advances in the areas of plurinationality, interculturality, and the rights of nature, in practice, there are still structural obstacles to guaranteeing the full exercise of these rights.

The Ecuadorian Constitution devotes a specific chapter to the rights of communities, Indigenous Peoples, and nationalities. This chapter recognizes collective rights related to the imprescriptible ownership of community lands, Indigenous justice, the conservation of biodiversity management practices, and participation in usufruct rights, administration, and conservation of natural resources in their territories. Likewise, the constitutional text establishes that the State must develop biodiversity conservation programs with community participation.

However, there are internal contradictions in the constitutional text itself and difficulties in transferring these recognitions to the practical sphere. One of the central reflections was the coexistence of constitutional provisions that, on the one hand, recognize broad collective rights and, on the other, concentrates in the central State exclusive competences over protected natural areas and natural resources. This tension generates uncertainty about the effective scope of Indigenous Peoples' participation and territorial control. While Article 57 recognizes rights linked to the administration and conservation of natural resources in Indigenous territories, Article 261 attributes exclusive competences to the State over these areas, generating a structural contradiction regarding which of these mandates prevails in practice.

The group also reflected critically on the implementation of the rights of nature. Although the country was recognized as an international reference for having incorporated these rights into the Constitution, there is a significant gap between legal recognition and concrete territorial results. For example, in the case of the Machángara River in Quito, recognition of rights to of the river itself was achieved judicially; and the municipality was sued for failing to comply with its protection obligations. However, the river continues to be highly polluted, which shows that regulatory advances do not necessarily translate into effective processes of restoration and environmental protection. The Ecuador group emphasized that the existence of constitutional rights does not automatically guarantee their implementation, which depends on political, institutional, and budgetary factors.

In relation to Free, Prior, and Informed Consent, Marilin explained that this right is recognized both in the Constitution and in ILO Convention 169, especially with activities of prospection, exploitation, and commercialization of non-renewable resources and administrative or legislative measures that may affect Indigenous Peoples. However, there are also important limitations in its implementation. Ecuador does not have its own robust prior consultation protocol. In many cases, simplified tools developed by the Ministry of the Environment or general references to Convention 169 are used, which shows insufficient regulation to guarantee adequate and culturally relevant processes.

FPIC should not be reduced to a procedural requirement, but should respect the timetables, dynamics, and organizational forms of Indigenous, peasant and Afro-descendant communities. As an example, the experience of processes promoted by CONFENIAE was shared, where some communities agreed to participate in certain initiatives, while others decided not to do so. This highlighted the possibility of rejecting projects as an essential aspect to effective exercise of this right.

Finally, the group linked the discussion to the constitutional principle of *Buen Vivir* (Good Living) or *sumak kawsay* in Quechua, understood as a dignified life based on harmony between people, communities, and nature. This vision implies recognizing nature not as an object of exploitation, but as a living being with which a relationship of coexistence and mutual respect is maintained. These rights should even include processes of regeneration and restoration in the face of extractive activities or monocultures, focused on the reconstruction of the life cycles of affected ecosystems and the application of these constitutional principles in public policies and concrete practices in the territories.

Nature is not an object of exploitation, rather it is a living being, with which we maintain a relationship of coexistence and mutual respect – Marilyn Mashinkias

Colombia: Natural Resources and Territorial Governance / Intercultural Institutions and Legal Pluralism

The Colombia group focused its analysis on intercultural institutions and legal pluralism, considering that this axis makes it possible to articulate dimensions related to territorial governance, Indigenous autonomy, and coordination between different levels of government. Based on the Colombian constitutional framework, the group stressed that Colombia is a pluralistic, multicultural, and decentralized State, which opens a legal space for recognition of Indigenous territories as territorial entities with political, fiscal, and administrative autonomy. However, they also noted that many of these developments have faced limitations, stemming from the absence of comprehensive legislation that fully regulates the place of Indigenous territories within the state structure.

Thus, Juana explained that the group decided to focus precisely on this axis because the constitutional recognition of legal pluralism was initially formulated in a very general way, such that many of the subsequent transformations have had to be built in the midst of regulatory gaps.

Juan David mentioned that in the absence of a specific organic law, a good part of the regulatory advances have been developed through decrees issued by the executive branch. These have particularly included areas related to environmental coordination, the decentralization of education and health systems, and the strengthening of competencies of Indigenous authorities. But he also stressed that the Colombian model of decentralization does recognize Indigenous territories as part of the territorial structure of the State.

One of the most significant advances has been the shift from vertical relations to coordination schemes between Indigenous governments and national or local governments. In this sense, Juana pointed out that "the great advance is that today we managed to at least say that we can coordinate from government to government", which has allowed us to move towards processes of regulatory co-creation. These processes are not limited to prior consultation, but involve a new joint construction between state delegates, Indigenous authorities, and in some cases, civil society organizations. This experience was presented as a concrete expression of legal pluralism and intercultural institutionality, based on the idea that "only by working together is it possible for this to materialize."

Inter-governmental articulation does not end with the production of norms but extends to the implementation of public policies. Juana emphasized that "it is not only the co-creation of norms, but that implementation is also done jointly." This highlights the active role of Indigenous organizations in the monitoring, execution, and evaluation of public policies. Likewise, the existence of Indigenous organizational bodies at different territorial levels –

national, departmental and local – has strengthened the capacity of the Colombian Indigenous movement to have political and legal influence.

Finally, the group identified specific relevant experiences within the strengthening of legal pluralism. Juan David highlighted Decree 1232, specific to Indigenous Peoples in isolation. He noted that "we are the only country in the region that recognizes intercultural research within the research process of isolated Indigenous Peoples," centralizing cultural approaches and Indigenous participation. He also mentioned Decree 1275, which recognizes environmental competencies of Indigenous authorities. This process had the support of the Constitutional Court and is an example of progressive expansion of Indigenous self-government and territorial governance within the Colombian constitutional framework.

When Indigenous territories are recognized as territorial entities, they have the rights of territorial entities, such as political autonomy, fiscal autonomy and administrative autonomy. This is in addition to being rights holders within the constitutional framework that protects rights of Indigenous Peoples and has been developed through different normative instruments. – Juan David Varela

Peru: Territorial Rights and Land Tenure / Natural Resources and Territorial Governance / Participation and Free, Prior, and Informed Consent

This group agreed that the Peruvian legal framework recognizes certain collective rights of Indigenous Peoples, but maintains important structural limitations derived from the predominance of state control over territories and natural resources. In this context, the group highlighted the tensions between the formal recognition of rights, the legal categories in force, and the real possibilities of exercising Indigenous territorial autonomy.

In relation to territorial rights and land tenure, Silvana explained that in Peru, collective rights do not directly recognize Indigenous Peoples as political subjects, but through community legal constructs: "rights are not granted to the people as such, but to peasant and native communities," which configures a fragmented model of recognition. Likewise, the territorial and tenure regime is mixed. "The capacity of the forest is maintained in the name of the State, while the agricultural portion is adjudicated." This implies that while lands suitable for agriculture can be awarded as communal property, forest areas remain under state ownership and are handed over under cessation of use statutes. This situation has been criticized by Indigenous Peoples for limiting the full recognition of their ancestral territories.

The group also addressed the case of territorial reserves and Indigenous reserves for Peoples in voluntary isolation. They pointed out that although these legal constructs recognize forms of ancestral occupation, legal ownership remains in State hands. As for the regime of communal reserves, it is also a mixed model of co-management between the State and Indigenous communities, where the communities maintain certain territorial rights while the protected natural area remains under state administration.

In the axis of natural resources and territorial governance, Hugo explained that the Peruvian legal system is based on the principle that "natural resources are the patrimony of the nation," which means that the State retains control over their administration and grants usufruct rights through authorizations or concessions. This logic generates a restrictive regime for Indigenous Peoples, since "any use for commercial purposes requires an express authorization from the State." Communities can carry out uses considered subsistence or self-consumption, but the legislation does not clearly define these concepts, which produces wide margins of discretion and frequent conflicts.

A central tension in Peru is the overlapping of rights over the same territory. Hugo explained that "there may be a community that has its own forest management entity, but at the same time, the State grants a hydrocarbon concession," creating a socio-environmental conflict. This overlapping of mining, forestry, and/or hydrocarbon concessions on communal territories is one of the main sources of territorial conflict.

Also, communal reserves operate through shared management contracts with the State. The co-management roles of the community are mainly limited to surveillance and monitoring functions. There is still no full intercultural regime that substantively incorporates Indigenous knowledge systems in territorial and environmental management. Andrea clarified that many of these tensions are not only legal tensions, but directly affect the daily life and concrete ways that communities exercise territorial control and the use of natural resources.

With respect to the axis of participation and Free, Prior, and Informed Consent, Peru has a specific law on prior consultation and sectoral regulations, with certain jurisprudence developed; however, significant difficulties remain in its implementation. Even though some Indigenous Peoples have developed their own consultation protocols, their recognition and application remain uneven. In practice, consultation is usually carried out when State decisions have already been adopted or advanced, limiting the real possibilities of advocacy of Indigenous Peoples. In addition, the State retains the power to make final decisions even when there is no agreement, which restricts the effective scope of consent. Finally, important gaps were also identified in terms of financing, since limited budgets cannot guarantee adequate processes of participation, translation, internal deliberation, and technical support.

The group's reflections showed that the Peruvian case continues to be marked by strong state centralization over natural resources and territories and by persistent tensions between formally recognized collective rights and the real conditions for their effective exercise.

Peruvian legislation recognizes natural resources as part of the national patrimony. ... The State has administrative authority and cedes and grants rights. That ends up generating a principle of subsistence.... There may be a community that has its forest, management entity, but at the same time, the State grants a hydrocarbon concession, generating a set of conflicts – Hugo Che Piu

4. Final reflection in plenary and closing of the day

After the group presentations, Jon proposed a brief dynamic to close the day's work and collect individual learnings derived from the discussions. He invited participants to stand up and form pairs, noting: "I want everyone to get up and form pairs." He explained that the objective was to share with another person a significant element that each one took away from the day, proposing as a conversation guide "something useful that you are going to take away from this discussion." This space allowed participants to identify comparative learning and possible lines of future articulation.

Processing in plenary, Hugo highlighted the discussions on models of Indigenous self-governance, noting that one of the elements that most impacted him was the Bolivian experience. Hugo raised the need to deepen these experiences comparatively, stating that "a deeper discussion on models of self-governance would be ideal. ... I'm already taking a lot of knowledge, but I'd like more." He also highlighted the level of legal and political recognition of Indigenous Peoples in Bolivia, and proposed moving towards new spaces for regional exchange aimed at mutual learning and articulation between national experiences.

Maria especially valued the comparative exercise, highlighting its usefulness to understand the differences between the legal frameworks of the different Amazonian countries. "The exercise of making this type of chart and analysis is super useful," because it allows identifying "how far you can go in a country according to its legal framework," as well as recognizing both opportunities and limitations within each national context. She stressed that the comparative analysis not only contributes to understanding existing restrictions, but also to visualize strategic possibilities for action and advocacy. This exercise "gives a perspective of opportunities as well."

Tita made a general comment on Day 2 labors, recognizing the collective effort and the intensity of the discussions. She recapped that the day had been marked by two major collective exercises: one aimed at building a shared understanding on the relationships between conservation and Indigenous rights in the different Amazonian countries, and another focused on the discussion of "innovative strategies". Regarding this second axis, she stressed that "new words and new definitions were released, and some incredible examples emerged" for further group exploration.

Tita also linked the day's learnings with workshop objectives, noting that discussions have made it possible to advance reflection on the impacts of Indigenous governance instruments on protections of territories, rights, and life in the Amazon. In addition, she indicated that the collective work had contributed to critically evaluating the effectiveness of existing legal frameworks and identifying experiences effective in territorial defense and Indigenous rights strengthening. She stressed that the exchange had highlighted strategies and processes "that have been effective and positive for the protection of Indigenous Peoples, their rights, their territories."

Finally, she anticipated the following day's exercise that will invite participants to delve more deeply into the experiences and discussions that have generated the greatest interest. She

proposed conceiving the next session as "a fair of innovative experiences, a fair of positive examples", aimed at sharing concrete cases of learning, achievements, and challenges in the defense of Indigenous territories and rights.

Figure 13. Workshop participants during plenary discussion

DAY 3: BEST STRATEGIES IN ACTION

The day began with a welcome and group reflection activity, in which participants were invited to share a recent moment of joy linked to their personal or work lives. Stories associated with reunions, professional achievements, collective processes, and territorial experiences emerged. In this space, two new participants were also introduced, Cecilia and Sarai Gómez from IUCN, who briefly presented their work on rights-based conservation, with an emphasis on Indigenous Peoples, women, and youth.

Feedback from the previous day summarized key learnings. Participants recalled the initial work of building common concepts (innovation, self-governance, conservation, and Indigenous rights) and the comparative analysis of national regulatory frameworks. From this, Tita presented the dynamics for the day: a "Fair of Experiences", where the groups would present around 10 specific cases, collectively prioritized. These priority experiences would be worked on during the day, respecting the limited time available, and maintaining as a central principle mutual listening and participation of all voices.

Figure 14. Guide for the preparation of the stand

Figure 15. Stands' preparation

1. Groups and experiences shared at the Fair

Stand 1: Macroterritory of the Jaguares de Yuruparí

Members: Antonio and Juan David

Antonio and Juan David presented the Macroterritory of the Yuruparí Jaguars, highlighting it as an experience of complex Indigenous governance, with important advances but also intersected by multiple challenges. The decision to present this case responded to the group's desire to share an experience considered significant and positive in terms of territorial, political, and legal articulation.

Antonio explained that the macro-territory is understood as a space for articulation between several Amazonian Indigenous governments, which have established political and cultural agreements to coexist and coordinate in the same expanded territorial area, strengthening their autonomy and their own forms of government. In his words, it is a process that articulates different Indigenous governments in the Colombian Amazon, where interterritorial coordination has made it possible to advance in the political recognition of the

space and in its dialogue with the State. He pointed out the key roles of strategic allies, such as the Gaia Amazonas Foundation, and international cooperation, which have accompanied organizational and legal strengthening.

He also mentioned that the macro-territory is located in the Colombian Amazon region (in the Departments of Amazonas and Guaviare) and has implied relevant transformations in the relationship with the State, particularly in the recognition of its own forms of territorial planning. In this process, dialogues have been developed with entities such as the National Land Agency and the Geographic Institute (IGAC) to advance formalization and recognition processes.

Juan David pointed out that one of the central impacts of the process has been the strategic use of the law, especially through tutela actions and decisions of the Constitutional Court, making visible and protecting the macro-territory against multiple risks. Since 2021, several relevant rulings have been obtained from the Constitutional Court, including Judgment 306 of 2025, which recognizes the risk to the physical and cultural survival of the macro-territory from factors such as illegal mining, the presence of armed actors, and the lack of territorial formalization. This ruling includes multiple orders addressed to state entities and establishes a long-term framework for action. He also mentioned a case related to defense of the Indigenous government from implementation of a REDD+ project that was not recognized by the authorities of the territory itself.

Finally, they highlighted as a central challenge the need to consolidate the macro-territory as an example of coordination and intercultural dialogue. Overcoming traditional intermediation schemes, this consolidation allows a direct relationship between Indigenous governments, the State, and the private sector. Other challenges pointed out by Antonio were:

- a) Cultural: To guarantee the survival of Indigenous knowledge systems and identity in the face of institutional and external changes.
- b) Political-institutional: To strengthen articulation with the State, considering the difficulties in understanding the systems of Indigenous governments.
- c) Administrative: To consolidate management schemes, appropriate to Indigenous logics and recognized by the state legal system.
- d) Financial: To ensure sustainability through diversified strategies (international cooperation, decentralization, environmental instruments, and local economies).
- e) Planning: To develop their own autonomous systems for territorial management such as the Information System for Indigenous Territorial Management (SIGETI).
- f) To articulate Indigenous life plans with the National Development Plan, given that Indigenous governments are increasingly assuming direct management functions.

Questions and answers: In response to audience questions, Antonio explained that the macro-territory is organized into two levels: Community level, where each community has its own authorities and forms of government; and territorial level, where an Indigenous Council acts as the highest authority of the macro-territory and articulates decision-making between communities. Articulation with the State is carried out through sectoral channels, especially in education, health, and the environment, through direct coordination with relevant State ministries without intermediation from department level authorities.

Figure 16. Stand preparation and presentation of the experience Bottom of Form

The institutional design of the macro-territory is based on the constitutional recognition of Indigenous governments in Colombia, with the current objective to strengthen direct dialogue with the national level, reducing historical intermediations of departments. The special Indigenous jurisdiction (Article 246 of the Colombian Constitution) does not depend on the existence of Indigenous territorial entities, although territorial recognition strengthens its exercise. Regulatory gaps for coordination between the ordinary justice system and the Indigenous jurisdiction still exist and represent an open field for institutional development.

Antonio reflected on the importance of Indigenous jurisdiction based on cultural, spiritual, and community principles that extend beyond the administrative level. Although there have been advances, challenges remain in articulating with the state legal system, especially in relation to grounding conflict resolution on Indigenous knowledge systems, spiritual authorities, and sages.

Stand 2: Indigenous Peoples in Isolation and Initial Contact (PIACI)

Participants: María Fernanda (Mafer) and Juana

This group presented an experience focused on the protection of Indigenous Peoples in Isolation and Initial Contact (PIACI). Juana pointed out that the protection of PIACI constitutes “the DNA and the heart of its work” and structured the presentation on two levels: the case of Colombia and the regional work through the International Working Group of Peoples in Isolation and Initial Contact (GTI-PIACI).

The specific Colombian process of recognition and protection of these Peoples rests on more than a decade of work with investigations, overflights, and research since 2008. This lengthy process culminated in the issuance of Decree 1232 as a legal framework for protection. From a perspective of governance and legal pluralism, Juana stressed that the construction of norms is not limited to consultation processes, but also co-production of norms between the State and Indigenous Peoples, under the principle of maximizing autonomy.

Mafer explained that one of the main advances derived from the process has been the creation of an intangible territory for the protection of the PIACI, formalized through Resolution 244 that currently covers about one million hectares. This process was promoted by neighboring Indigenous authorities (Arica and Bau Caquetá), who voluntarily decided to allocate part of their territories for the protection of Peoples in isolation under internal non-intervention agreements. This case is considered successful because:

- The creation of a protected Peoples buffer zone is unprecedented in the country.
- The incorporation of the PIACI theme is new in community educational processes.
- The need for inter-institutional coordination is recognized.
- Protection is led from the local level and not exclusively from the central State.

Factors that allowed consolidation of the process include:

- Highly committed technical and political teams.
- Sustained work in pedagogy and community health.
- Building alliances within the state (non-confrontational approach).
- Constant Indigenous leadership on the public agenda.
- Taking advantage of international situations (e.g. COP16) for political advocacy.

On the other hand, continued challenges include: 1) the expansion of illegal economies (especially mining in border areas), 2) the permanent risk of forced contact with Peoples in isolation, and 3) the need for preventive strategies for territorial protection.

Juana explained that the work carried out by the WGI-PIACI involves a regional network created in 2019 that articulates 21 civil society and Indigenous organizations with representation from 8 countries in the Amazon region and beyond. This has allowed: 1) the construction of regional reports on the presence of PIACI, 2) the development of territorial analysis methodologies without direct contact, 3) a rapid response to emergencies between countries, 4) incidence in global spaces of biodiversity, climate, and human rights and 5) regional media articulation.

Questions and answers: The audience highlighted not only the territorial delimitation of the PIACI, but also the methodologies used. Especially given contexts of extractive pressure and infrastructure projects, combination of several techniques were employed: work with neighboring communities, reconstruct "territorial milestones" from oral memory, use satellite images for contrast, identify mobility patterns, jointly validate using traditional knowledge and technical analysis.

Official recognition of PIACI in Colombia requires extensive, rigorous, and costly research processes. These include a survey of cultural history and territorial evidence, methodological validation without direct contact, and a precise definition of the territory of protection. It was

emphasized that the main difficulty is not normative, but methodological with access to information, given that many of these Peoples do not leave visible traces.

In addition, to avoid dilution of responsibilities, a multisectoral platform is not used for decision-making, territorial recognition, and PIACI standards. The Ministry of the Interior is responsible for decisions, although the process begins at the local level with neighboring communities and then goes through national consultation spaces before formalization.

The protection of PIACI in Colombia has advanced significantly thanks to the articulation between territorial Indigenous knowledge, legal frameworks such as Decree 1232, inter-institutional alliances, and regional networks such as the GTI-PIACI. However, critical challenges remain related to extractive pressure, institutional sustainability, and the need to strengthen non-contact research methodologies.

Figura 17. Stand preparation and poster used during their presentation

Stand 3. Free, Prior, and Informed Consent (FPIC) in Peru

Members: Hugo, Cecilia, Juan David, Silvana, and Leonardo

The group presented the experience of prior consultation in Peru as a key mechanism, although not sufficient in itself, to guarantee Indigenous Peoples' rights. It was emphasized that prior consultation is not an autonomous substantive right, but a procedural tool that

enables the enforceability of other rights such as territory, self-determination, and self-government.

The process has been promoted mainly by AIDSESEP, in coordination with other Indigenous organizations and civil society, based on ILO Convention 169 ratified in the 1990s. However, its effective implementation did not begin until the mid-2000s, following a period of conflict marked by the approval of a forestry law without consultation. This led to national protests and the subsequent approval of the Law of Prior Consultation (2011). This process has been accompanied by court rulings and regulatory developments that have broadened its scope, including both the obligation to consult even when measures are considered "beneficial", and the development of consultation protocols by Indigenous Peoples themselves.

A recent milestone was the consultation on the National Policy on Indigenous Peoples, which consolidated a broad process of intersectoral dialogue and agreements between the State and Indigenous organizations.

Factors that have contributed to advancement of these processes include:

- International pressure and standards of ILO Convention 169.
- The leadership of the Amazonian Indigenous movement, especially AIDSESEP.
- Existence of national and international jurisprudence.
- Critical political junctures (socio-environmental conflicts).
- Regional comparative experiences.

Figure 18. Group Stand Preparation

On the other hand, main implementation challenges remain, such as the absence of a clear procedure for legislative consultation; weak follow-up and agreement compliance; inter-institutional conflicts over who wields consult authority; insufficient budgets to implement processes; the Civil Society Organization Support Unit; ambiguity over appropriate timeframes for consultation; and a restrictive State interpretation of "direct affectation". The definition of "direct affectation" is determined by the State itself, generating conflicts of interest. In practice, the Ministry of Culture acts as a decisive entity, although with frequent inter-institutional disputes.

Peruvian legislation does not recognize the right of veto, but the consultation seeks to reach agreements, although these can be judicially demanded. International standards (such as the Inter-American Court of Human Rights IACHR) do contemplate consent in cases of serious affectation, but these have not been fully incorporated into Peruvian regulations.

Conclusions: Despite its limitations, prior consultation has ended up consolidating itself as a necessary tool within Indigenous strategies. Although not ideal, it has become a pragmatic mechanism for influencing State decisions, especially in contexts where other rights have not yet been fully guaranteed.

Stand 4. Construction of Indigenous Territorial Autonomy in Bolivia

Members: Catalina, Juan Carlos and Leonardo

The group presented the case of the construction of an autonomous territory in Bolivia - the Multiethnic Indigenous Territory (TIM) They focused on the analysis on the struggle for territorial consolidation, the exercise of self-determination, and the construction of Indigenous self-government. Juan Carlos introduced the presentation by pointing out that the process can be summarized in the phrase: "struggle for the consolidation of the territory for the exercise of self-determination and autonomy".

Leonardo explained that this case reflects a historical vision of the Bolivian Amazonian Indigenous movement, where the defense of the territory was always linked to a long-term projection of Indigenous self-government. In fact, the political origin of the process is the 1990 Indigenous march "Territory and Dignity". It was led by Amazonian Indigenous Peoples in rejection of the subdivision of Indigenous territories for forest concessions. This mobilization permitted initial recognition of four Indigenous territories, including the TIM. Subsequently, the constitutional reform of 1994 recognized the Community Lands of Origin (CLO), purposefully overlooking the term "Indigenous territory" due to political tensions over the idea of territorial unity of the Bolivian State. From that moment on, the process of collective titling of the territory began.

A central milestone was the 2009 Political Constitution of the State, which incorporated recognition of the plurinational State, Indigenous self-determination, Indigenous autonomy, and legal pluralism. In 2010, Indigenous autonomy was formally acceded, transforming it into an autonomous Indigenous government under the constitutional model. Subsequently, the Autonomous statute was approved in 2017 with constitutional control, and in 2019, approximately 200,000 hectares previously excluded from the territory by forest concessions

were reinstated. Finally, between 2023 and 2024, a new Indigenous territorial unit was consolidated, and the autonomous Indigenous government was formally formed.

One of the main impacts of the process has been the transformation of Indigenous Peoples into central political actors at the regional and territorial levels. Similarly impactful was the creation of a new Indigenous government structure and the disappearance of the previous municipal fragmentation. Before, the territory was divided between different municipalities and provinces, while now it constitutes an autonomous territorial unit under Indigenous government.

The group also highlighted the creation of a conservation area within the Indigenous territory, recognized by Law 1497, as well as the strengthening of its own forms of ecological governance and territorial control. Juan Carlos explained that fundamental political decisions continue to be made through traditional structures within the Indigenous government: the *cabildos* (a local council) and meetings of *Corregidores* (judicial officials). Leonardo underlined the exclusion of political parties from the Indigenous government structure as an important political impact. He pointed out that many Indigenous autonomies emerged precisely as a strategy to prevent party logics from distorting community processes and Indigenous Peoples' own forms of decision-making.

Leonardo highlighted the importance of historical memory and organizational continuity in explaining the progress of this process. Many current leaders of this process are descendants or political heirs of those who led the 1990 Indigenous march. This has made it possible to maintain memory, political continuity in the territory, and a legal and constitutional strategy promoted by the Indigenous movement. Also that they opted to transform the legal and constitutional framework of the State to incorporate Indigenous rights within the State structure highlights the important role of legal advisors in the process.

Juan Carlos stressed that remaining challenges include the need to strengthen their own financing mechanisms and guarantee administrative capacity to sustain the new structure of an autonomous government. Because the autonomous structure withdrew from previous municipalities, they had to quickly assume responsibilities related to health, education, and public management.

Another main current challenge shifting between the traditional manner of organizing demands to one under the new Indigenous autonomous government. The legal ownership of the collective territory continues in the hands of the traditional organization – the sub-central of councils – while the autonomous government exercises the functions of territorial public management, which generates constant tensions over representation and exercise of authority.

Questions and answers: In the round of questions, Juan Carlos further detailed the structure of the autonomous Indigenous government. The executive body is headed by a cacique – a figure equivalent to a mayor – accompanied by an advisory council, legal advisors, an administrative secretariat, and technical staff responsible for social, cultural, environmental, and territorial planning. In addition, there is a territorial assembly with representation of the five Indigenous Peoples that inhabit the territory, in which Indigenous jurisdiction continues

to function through traditional communal structures. The Indigenous judicial body does not operate as a separate structure as in the State model but is exercised through already existing community authorities and mechanisms, which means that meetings of *Corregidores* remain the highest level of political and territorial decision-making.

In environmental matters, autonomous Indigenous governments have constitutionally recognized powers of control, oversight, and territorial management. Leonardo pointed out that the territory can create conservation areas and manages its natural resources under its own regulations, although he clarified that certain resources are still formally the patrimony of the Bolivian State, so authorization coordination with State entities continues. The Indigenous government can exercise territorial control over illegal activities such as timber piracy and it can develop mechanisms of articulation with other territories to protect the sources of shared rivers and watersheds.

Finally, in response to questions about the multiethnic nature of the territory, Juan Carlos explained that coexistence between different Indigenous Peoples has required sustained processes of intercultural dialogue, due to differences in language, customs, and ways of electing authorities. However, he pointed out that there are also shared spaces for cultural, festive, and ritual coexistence that have progressively strengthened political cohesion.

Figure 19. Stand preparation and presentation of the experience

Stand 5. Strengthening of Indigenous Peoples' Organizations (IPOs) with a Gender and Youth Focus

Members: Alex, Darío, Saraí, Yulissa, Marilyn and Nadia

This group presented a series of experiences aimed at strengthening IPOs through approaches focused on gender, youth, political training, communication, and legal strengthening. Unlike other cases focused on a single territorial or normative process, this presentation brought together various initiatives promoted by Indigenous organizations, international organizations, and support networks, united by a common objective to strengthen Indigenous youth and women's leadership for territorial defense, political participation, and organizational sustainability.

Nadia emphasized that the cross-cutting goal of these shared experiences was to strengthen organizations by promoting the active participation of Indigenous youth and women in the defense of collective rights and territories. The group highlighted various political, legal, and community training initiatives.

School of Amazonian Leadership and training of Indigenous youth.

Marilyn shared the experience of the Amazonian Leadership School promoted by CONFENIAE. This initiative was born in 2023 and to date, three cohorts have been developed, articulating various Amazonian organizations and 11 Indigenous nationalities of the Ecuadorian Amazon. The main objective has been to strengthen the capacities of Indigenous youth in the areas of human rights, environmental rights, leadership, territorial protection, and environmental protection.

She also stressed that the process has evolved into creating spaces for regional and binational exchange. In the third cohort, a binational school was developed with participation of Amazonian Indigenous youth from Peru, with intentions to consolidate a future regional Amazonian training platform between Ecuador and Peru.

Marilyn pointed out that one of the most important impacts of the process has been the progressive incorporation of Indigenous youth into organizational leadership spaces. Several participants are currently part of government councils and hold positions of presidency, communication, youth, and community leadership.

Governance reforms with a gender perspective.

Saraí presented an experience promoted by IUCN together with Indigenous organizations of the Shuar people and the Shiwiari nationality of Ecuador. This initiative aims to strengthen women's political participation within Indigenous governance instruments. She explained that, although women actively participated in organizations, such participation was not adequately reflected in governance instruments such as Life Plans and Governing Statutes. In one case, there were even explicit provisions preventing women from holding presidential positions in the Governing Councils.

The reform process arose from demands of Indigenous women within the organizations. Training and collective reflection sessions were held with joint participation of men and women, seeking to avoid confrontational approaches and promote a shared understanding of the importance of women's political participation in community governance.

As results, she highlighted the incorporation of a specific chapter on Indigenous women in one of the Life Plans, progress in the reform of organizational statutes, and the possibility for women to access vice-presidential positions in Governing Councils. Although it was not possible to fully enable women to hold the presidency, Sarai stressed that the process opened up important spaces to politically recognize women within Indigenous organizational structures.

Indigenous legal training and advocacy networks.

Nadia and Alex presented the project "Practices of Indigenous legal advocacy", which between 2019 and 2024, counted with participation of Indigenous attorneys from different Brazilian territories. The project articulated legal training, leadership and organizational strengthening through international exchanges, working groups, territorial immersions, political training, and specific spaces for Indigenous female lawyers.

They also pointed out that all the participants had scholarships and participated in collective processes of knowledge production and dissemination of materials. A central element was to connect legal training and concrete territorial realities. This was particularly important within a context marked by the pandemic and the government of Jair Bolsonaro that was characterized by critical tensions around Indigenous rights in Brazil. This context clarified the need to consolidate Indigenous advocacy networks committed to territorial defense and collective rights, while also generating professional opportunities and institutional endorsements for participants.

Questions and answers: During the round of questions, Maria asked what factors may have facilitated the appropriation and sustainability of the learning generated by these initiatives. In response, Nadia pointed out that the political and health context of the pandemic was a key factor that strengthened bonds of solidarity and articulation between Indigenous organizations and professionals. The existence of a "common enemy" in Brazil reduced internal tensions and favored construction of collaboration networks sustained over time. She stressed that many Indigenous lawyers were already doing volunteer work in defense of territorial rights, so the project made it possible to strengthen existing capacities and professionalize processes that were already being developed from the territories.

Marilin explained that the sustainability of the Amazonian Leadership School is based on the permanent relationship with the territorial organizations of origin of the young participants. She pointed out that the cohorts maintain processes of monitoring, replication and territorial feedback, ensuring that the training and its impacts are not limited to specific events. She also highlighted the role of strategic allies and the importance of trainers originating from Indigenous Peoples and nationalities, thus strengthening horizontal processes of knowledge circulation. In addition, she mentioned the role of a community communication collective

"Lancers Digitales", active since 2017, as an important tool to strengthen their own communication skills and make territorial processes visible through digital platforms.

Figure 20. Group experiences

Yulissa added that another fundamental factor is timely identification of youth leadership within the communities. Continuous accompaniment and monitoring of training processes foment consolidation of sustainable youth networks and in the medium term, improves chances that these young people assume leadership positions within Indigenous organizations.

Follow-up comments by Silvana and Catalina pointed out the existing difficulties in obtaining funding specifically for processes with Indigenous children and youth within the framework of territorial and environmental strategies. They proposed moving towards the creation of a regional space for pan-Amazonian articulation aimed at exchanging experiences to strengthen youth and communication processes; to develop common financing strategies; and to articulate existing territorial initiatives.

Catalina particularly emphasized the need to train Indigenous journalists and communicators with a territorial and environmental approach and capable of communicating autonomous processes, territorial conflicts, and experiences of environmental defense from the communities themselves. Juana also highlighted the existence of regional experiences in community monitoring with children, bird watching, and work on Indigenous Peoples in isolation and intercultural educational processes.

Conclusion: Overall, the group stressed that one of the central challenges is to guarantee the political, organizational, and financial sustainability of these training and strengthening processes, preventing them from depending exclusively on short-term projects or discontinuous external support.

Figure 21. Members of the stand during the presentation of their experiences

Stand 6. Articulation of legal action and Indigenous territorial defense in Brazil

Members: Rafael and Wânia

This group presented on the articulation between Indigenous rights defense, legal actions, and Indigenous-driven organizational and territorial processes in the face of growing conflict. In Brazil, Indigenous Peoples currently face multiple territorial, political, and legal threats that have led them to strengthen legal and organizational strategies for the protection of their collective rights and their territories.

Territorial conflicts take place in profoundly unequal scenarios of power, where external actors—including economic sectors and political pressure groups—maintain close relations with state institutions and security forces. This hinders effective access to justice and territorial protection. Indigenous communities are constantly forced to resort to legal actions, institutional negotiations, and advocacy mechanisms to defend rights that are already formally recognized.

They also stressed that legal defense cannot be understood in isolation but must be considered in relation to Indigenous organizational processes and internal strengthening. This group

underscored the importance of consolidating Indigenous led training and training processes, mentioning the role of Indigenous mentors, teachers, and administrative and financial teams in sustaining educational and organizational initiatives within Indigenous structures.

The group also emphasized that in this context of strong institutional and judicial pressure, Indigenous organizations must increasingly assume technical and political responsibilities to sustain litigation, advocacy processes, and territorial defense strategies. They indicated that many communities are constantly negotiating with State bodies and political actors to guarantee respect for their rights, especially in the face of legislative and economic initiatives that threaten their territories and ways of life.

Finally, Rafael and Wânia stressed that territorial defense requires permanent articulation between legal action, organizational strengthening, strategic communication, and alliance building. They pointed out that protection of territories and biodiversity depends to a large extent on the capacity of Indigenous organizations to sustain collective processes, strengthen their internal cohesion, and assume in a shared manner the responsibilities linked to the defense of collective and territorial rights.

Figure 22. Group Stand Preparation

Questions and answers: Silvana raised an open reflection on the internal conflicts that many Indigenous communities go through when external actors promote internal divisions through economic incentives, differentiated political relations, or community fragmentation strategies. She specifically asked, "What happens when half of the people do not agree?",

referring to scenarios in which extractive projects, companies, or other actors manage to generate internal fractures within the communities regarding territorial or political decisions. This type of situation is one of the most complex challenges for territorial governance and defense processes, as it affects community cohesion and weakens internal organizational capacities.

Finally, she raised the need to continue reflecting collectively on how to accompany these processes of fragmentation and internal conflict, recognizing that these are problems that not only affect Indigenous Peoples, but also various territories and communities in the region.

Stand 7. Intercultural and regional alliances for the Amazon

Members: Luisa and Carolina

This initiative seeks to maintain the functionality of an entire system that is interconnected and interdependent and to build an agenda of impact and political advocacy to safeguard the ecological, sociocultural, and territorial integrity of the Pan-Amazon region. The proposal is based on an intercultural dialogue of knowledge between Indigenous Peoples and civil society organizations that have historically accompanied Amazonian territorial processes. The objective is to generate synergies between Indigenous knowledge systems and experiences accumulated by social and environmental organizations, building a common agenda for regional advocacy.

Carolina explained that this articulation brings together a wide diversity of Amazonian networks and actors, including the Network of Amazonian Regional Networks, the Scientific Panel for the Amazon, watershed transmission networks, faith community networks, territorial monitoring networks, the International Working Group of Peoples in Isolation and Initial Contact (GTI-PIACI), the Coordinator of Indigenous Organizations of the Amazon Basin (COICA), and Indigenous organizations from different Amazonian countries. This is a recent 2025 initiative that emerged in response to the advance of multiple threats to the Amazon biome and Indigenous territories.

Although the process is still incipient, important advances in regional political articulation have already been accomplished. A key achievement was the building of consensus among multiple regional networks of civil society and Indigenous organizations around a shared agenda of Amazonian transformation. This process facilitated a joint advocacy mission at the COP of the United Nations Framework Convention on Climate Change (UNFCCC), constituting one of the first milestones of regional intercultural articulation.

A main lesson learned has been to identify synergies between civil society agendas and those of Indigenous Peoples - to recognize common points in the visions of change and to understand that both parties have complementary capacities to influence national and international decision-making spaces. The alliance has begun to project a joint agenda of political advocacy aimed at actively participating in regional and global spaces where Amazonian policies are defined. The objective is to transcend discourse and consolidate concrete mechanisms for advocacy and regional action.

The process aims to consolidate a new Amazonian regional political entity, composed of Indigenous organizations, civil society networks, and other regional actors capable of promoting a shared agenda for the comprehensive biome protection. This intercultural dialogue seeks to progressively expand to other Peoples and actors historically less visible in regional discussions.

Luisa added that this alliance is built on intercultural dialogue between political agendas and rights guarantee perspectives, identifying convergences between diverse policy priorities to build a shared vision of protecting the Amazon "beyond regional borders."

This commitment seeks to go beyond traditional institutional frameworks of Amazonian cooperation, proposing an expanded regional vision to protect against growing risks such as the Amazonian tipping point. In operational terms, the first major collective action was organized around the COP through construction of the Intercultural Climate Pact. The objective was to position the Amazon at the center of the regional and global climate agenda, generating collective versus fragmented actions capable of amplifying regional political advocacy.

Common axes of regional advocacy, including regional climate governance, financing and climate justice, mitigation and adaptation, and just transitions were defined. All are based on fundamental rights of Indigenous Peoples, such as self-determination, the right to territory, prior consultation and consent. The alliance seeks to build an agenda of political advocacy sustained over time and not limited only to specific conjunctures or specific international events.

Main achievements included construction of consensus among 12 regional civil society networks that brought together more than 650 organizations. This process required ample spaces for dialogue to agree on common priorities and build a shared minimum Amazonian agenda. The role played by Colombia in the General Secretariat of ACTO, and the existence of institutional actors open to strengthening the Amazonian regional articulation partially facilitated dialogue. However, Luisa and Carolina also indicated that the work was possible because many of the participating networks and organizations had already previously developed relatively consolidated agendas and priorities of their own, which facilitated the identification of points of convergence and the construction of a common political narrative.

Among main challenges, Luisa stressed the need to sustain regional articulation beyond specific situations, preventing the agenda from depending solely on international events or specific crises. She pointed out central challenge to consolidate permanent mechanisms for joint work and to strengthen the political legitimacy of the intercultural process. She also highlighted the need to develop more concrete tools to operationalize intercultural dialogue and translate it into effective mechanisms for implementation and regional governance.

Ensuring that territorial and Indigenous governance strategies provide a systemic vision of the Amazon biome and not perceived as isolated experiences is another important challenge. The alliance seeks to articulate diverse territorial processes within a regional logic aimed at preserving the ecological and sociocultural functioning of the Amazon.

Carolina added that another challenge is to recognize the importance of expanding intercultural dialogue to other knowledge systems and other historically invisible actors, including Afro-Amazonian peoples. She indicated that a next strategic step is to translate the vision of the Amazon as an integral system into concrete political and technical tools, capable of guiding non-fragmented regional policies and strengthening the construction of joint action agreements.

Figure 23. Presentation of group stand

Questions and answers: Mafer asked about involvement of actors from the Venezuelan Amazon and about the effective territorial scope of the alliance in Venezuela. In response, Carolina and Luisa pointed out that there are Venezuelan organizations linked to the process, although in a limited way and mainly through Amazonian regional networks. Some organizations are especially involved in initiatives related to ecological connectivity, biological corridors, and work with Indigenous Peoples. Articulations linked to institutional dynamics of ACTO also exist, particularly on issues related to fire management, environmental monitoring, and regional environmental networks.

Maria asked about the alliance relationship with Amazonian governments and about the most effective narratives to influence decision-makers to form a comprehensive vision of Amazonia. Luisa responded that the relationship with governments is heterogeneous and depends on the political orientations of each Amazonian country. However, some governments are more open to comprehensive approaches to Amazon protection, particularly highlighting Colombia and Brazil on issues related to ecological corridors and a functioning biome.

Carolina added that formal recognition of permanent participation mechanisms for Indigenous Peoples and civil society within the Amazonian regional architecture still faces important political limitations. But she pointed out that there are opportunities for practical advocacy through ACTO technical working groups, which have begun to solicit inputs and recommendations from Indigenous organizations and Amazonian civil society networks.

Figure 24. Presentation of the group

Stand 8. Indigenous Governance in Protected Areas

Members: Walter, Catalina, Andrea and Silvana

A comparison between Indigenous protected area governance experiences in Bolivia and Peru was presented at this stand. The objective was to analyze Indigenous Peoples' participation in conservation and decision-making within protected area systems, highlighting that, although protected areas and Indigenous presence exist in all countries, not in all contexts do Indigenous Peoples actively participate in management. The analysis began by examining the national systems of protected areas and moved towards concrete forms of Indigenous management in these protected territories.

Walter noted that the Peruvian case has a system of protected areas first consolidated with the 1970s creation of national parks, then establishment of the National System of Natural Areas Protected by the State in 1990, and the Law of Natural Protected Areas in 1997. Since 2008, the system has been managed by the National Service of Natural Areas Protected by the State (SERNANP), which administers national, regional and private protected areas. Peru currently has approximately 77 protected natural areas, organized into various conservation categories, including intangible national parks, national reserves, historical sanctuaries, and reserved areas.

In response to Indigenous demands to expand their communal territories and tensions with the State regarding productive use of land, the creation of a new category of communal reserves was promoted as a mechanism for direct participation of Indigenous Peoples in conservation. Currently, there are 11 communal reserves, the first being created in 1988 in the Pasco region. In 2002, the Amarakaeri Communal Reserve was established, highlighting its historical, territorial, and cultural importance for its Indigenous inhabitants.

For Walter, communal reserves can be understood as a form of State recognition of Indigenous ancestral territories, pointing out that "when we talk about communal reserves, we are talking about ancestral territories, now recognized as protected natural areas." In Peru, the management of these areas is governed by an administration contract of indefinite duration between the State and Indigenous organizations, which he referred to as "a marriage that will never end." That even if State institutions in charge change, "the contract will not cease to exist." The management model adopted is co-management, which implies shared intercultural governance between the State and Indigenous Peoples.

The **Amarakaeri Communal Reserve** integrates three Indigenous Peoples and several native communities, as well as regional and intermediate Indigenous organizations. Together with adjoining communal territories, more than half a million hectares are preserved. The co-management model is based on articulation between the state entity responsible for protected areas, the executor of the administration contract that represents Indigenous Peoples, and a management committee that articulates public and private actors. This co-management is "an intercultural exercise" based on three fundamental principles: an intercultural approach, transparency understood as reciprocal accountability between communities and the State, and the building of trust between the parties.

Catalina explained the cultural and historical origin of the Bolivian **Loma Santa Conservation Area**, pointing out that its creation is based on the memory and historical trajectories of different Indigenous Peoples. The area involves "five peoples, including the Mojeños, the Movimas, the Yuracarés," and the Chimanes - all Peoples who have maintained ways of life closely linked to the forest. Historically, several of these peoples—particularly the Mojeños and Yuracarés—sought to escape exploitative conditions during the rubber era, which led to a long pilgrimage in search of an ideal territory that "they called Loma Santa." This search lasted for more than a hundred years, and the current place was symbolically recognized as the territory that materializes that "ideal world", which is why the name of Loma Santa was given to the conservation area.

The conservation area of close to 200,000 hectares was recently created. Main achievements have been legal support for its recognition and creation of a control and surveillance system based on the organizational forms of the territory itself. The control system is supported by approximately 60 Chimane rangers who carry out territorial surveillance during their daily hunting and fishing activities, warning about threats and activating complaint mechanisms through their own organizational structures.

Catalina stressed that the main challenge lies in strengthening conservation area management within a context of Indigenous autonomous government that does not have the same fiscal resources as municipalities, forcing us to rethink sustainability mechanisms. The aim is to articulate traditional knowledge with technological tools and scientific knowledge. This includes installation of meteorological stations for drought and flood prevention, in addition to Chimane interpretations of the moon to anticipate climatic events. Another example is integration of wildlife management practices – e.g. protection of the jaguar for its role in forest balance – within an environmental management system that strengthens protected area governance.

Elements highlighted in the comparative analysis included different levels of decision-making and opportunities for Indigenous participation in conservation. Catalina emphasized that, based on the constitutional changes in Bolivia, territories can be autonomous governments and Indigenous governments to have the authority to create protected areas. This is a big difference compared to other countries, where the creation and management of protected areas remain centralized in the State.

She also stressed that, although there are advances in the recognition of protected area co-management, these processes are not homogeneous. In the Bolivian case, there are eight Indigenous governments, but only two have protected areas. This shows that implementation of Indigenous authority still faces territorial, political and administrative limits. Still, examples of concrete progress include the case of Charagua in the Chaco that has four Indigenous-created protected areas and the Amazonian case of the TIM, whose Indigenous protected area was created in 2024.

The group concluded that these processes come with articulation challenges between Indigenous governance and state conservation systems. Co-management involves negotiating competencies, resources, and responsibilities between levels of government. For this reason, it is necessary to strengthen the technical and political capacities of Indigenous governments so that they can effectively exercise their recognized authority in environmental and territorial management matters.

Questions and answers: Mafer asked about the relationship between Indigenous protected areas and State entities, especially the coordination, regulation, and articulation mechanisms between Indigenous governments and the Ministry of Environment. Catalina explained that in the case of Bolivia, Indigenous protected areas "are part of the national system, but they do not receive funds from the government." Public financing is concentrated in protected areas at the national level, while departmental governments finance departmental areas, and municipalities theirs. Indigenous protected areas must autonomously manage their own resources for protected area function and sustainability.

Walter explained that, in Peru, the system of protected areas is under the Ministry of the Environment and that institutions such as SERNANP and the Peruvian Forest Service are part of that scheme. Unlike Bolivia, no direct funds are allocated to the executor of the contract for administration of communal reserves.

Figure 25. Preparation of the group stand and presentation of the experiences

Walter and Catalina listed main threats faced by AmaraKaeri and Loma Santa, respectively: illegal hunting, illegal trespassing by truck to extract resources, wildlife trafficking, illegal mining, and informal settlements. The Madre de Dios region, although recognized for its biodiversity, faces high levels of illegality that affect community territories, including mining, drug trafficking, unplanned or planned roads without Indigenous participation, and hydrocarbon extractive activities. Walter added that in 2024 there were even threats and murders, which has led to strengthening surveillance, monitoring, and security plans.

Walter explains that although there is a state security system headed by the Ministry of the Interior, in practice, it has not been effective in protecting Indigenous territories due to structural problems such as corruption and collusion by state actors with illegal economies. For example, after the 2024 murders, multisectoral meetings were activated at high decision-making levels within the Ministries of Justice, Interior, Environment, and the Public Prosecutor's Office, resulting in installation of permanent police posts. However, the police presence has not guaranteed real protection, since in some cases, new forms of extortion and conflict with communities have ensued, which has even led to community rejection of these checkpoints. There is a deep distrust in the State's protection mechanisms, which are slow and ineffective in the face of the urgency of threats, which is why the Indigenous are currently

working on constructing their own prevention, surveillance, and rapid response plan for defense of territory and life.

Catalina that the TIM has implemented its own system of territorial control and surveillance backed by a specific law. This system is based on actions of unpaid community rangers who travel the territory and the installation of fixed checkpoints at critical junctures where illegal settlements entered. This mechanism adopts traditional forms of territorial control and is activated in a community way in the face of conflicts or illegal entries. An example cited was an irregular entry by people from another Indigenous territory. This attempt was stopped at checkpoints and resolved with community mobilization, showing that the surveillance systems themselves allow for a collective and timely reaction to threats.

Stand 9. Cross-border efforts against illegalities

Members: Hugo, Andrea and Silvana

The group presented a cross-border experience that confronts illegalities affecting Amazonian Indigenous territories, especially illegal mining and its impacts on environmental defenders. Silvana explained that the initiative arises from the need to "join forces and transcend borders and legalities." It is based on articulation between Indigenous and civil society organizations that seek to respond to a common problem from their different experiences and in a coordinated manner. The central theme is protection of territories and defenders against illegal economies that operate transnationally and generate high levels of violence and pressure on Indigenous communities.

This process has been expanding its scope to include political advocacy, information production, and collective protection. Silvana explained that these alliances are expressed in regional and national platforms such as the "Observatory of Illegal Mining in Peru" and the "Alliance for the Reduction of Gold Mining Impacts in Colombia". These articulations were strengthened in global spaces, particularly at the COP on Biodiversity and Climate Change, where different organizations began to coordinate actions to make visible the impacts of mining on biodiversity and on environmental defenders.

Hugo delved into the experience of the **Illegal Mining Observatory in Peru**, pointing out that it is a broad articulation of organizations that work together against illegal mining. A main strength of the observatory is the production of territorial and scientific information, thanks to the work of institutions specialized in Amazonian monitoring and knowledge generation. He also highlighted the interactions between political and legal advocacy organizations, which allows evidence to be translated into proposals for regulatory change and public action.

Andrea and Silvana emphasized that the current context has worsened due to historic increases in the international price of gold, which intensifies pressures on Amazonian territories. All agreed that permanent strengthening of strategic planning and regional coordination is needed in lieu of increasingly complex and cross-border threats. Illegal mining cannot be understood in isolation, as it is linked to other criminal dynamics.

Hugo delved into the risks faced by territorial defenders against these illegal economies, pointing out that Indigenous organizations and leaders directly confront organized crime structures that react with threats and violence. In response, the Latin American Alliance of Defenders of Indigenous Territory (ALADTI) has been created, composed of organizations from different countries in the region. This network works through mechanisms of transnational solidarity and mutual support, activating when there are threats or situations of imminent risk. The alliance has developed protection mechanisms to support threatened defenders with funds, security, evacuation, and accompaniment measures.

Silvana also presented the **Zero Tolerance Initiative (ZTI)**, a global network aimed at urgent protection of environmental defenders on different continents. This initiative works through rapid response mechanisms, mobilizing resources for evacuations, relocations, and protection measures in contexts of extreme threat. The strategy seeks to reduce risks for defenders through advocacy actions and international pronouncements made from other countries or regions to avoid further exposing those who are in the territory. The initiative functions especially in contexts related to mining, corruption, and organized crime. In countries such as Peru, multiple protection and emergency evacuation measures have already been activated.

The group highlighted that a main impact of these articulations has been to strengthen the political advocacy and participation of Indigenous representatives in different national and international decision-making spaces. They also pointed out that production of evidence and the positioning of the issue in multilateral agendas have allowed important advances, particularly in international processes related to mining and mercury. As an example, they mentioned the advocacy developed within the framework of the Minamata Convention, where proposals promoted by organizations from Peru, Colombia, and Brazil were incorporated.

Finally, the group stressed that threats derived from illegal economies have exceeded local or national response capacities, which requires construction of broad, coordinated, and sustained coalitions over time. Contexts of weakening of rights, reduction of spaces for participation, and financing limitations has been a key challenge in a global scenario where rising gold prices increase pressure on Amazonian territories. They reported that next steps include the strengthening of territorial monitoring systems, information platforms, and transnational litigation strategies, including the possibility of activating mechanisms of the inter-American system or the international criminal system to address violations linked to illegal mining and violence against defenders.

Questions and answers from the group: The audience emphasized the importance of producing solid evidence and positioning it in international spaces to make visible the impacts of illegal mining on Indigenous territories and defenders. They highlighted the use of United Nations reports and mechanisms to strengthen political advocacy. One of the most relevant advances cited was the incorporation of regional alliance proposals within the framework of the Minamata Convention on mercury. This was considered an important political achievement and a collective responsibility to continue strengthening the regional agenda.

Threats linked to illegal mining and criminal economies require coordinated responses between organizations, countries, and state actors, since these are problems that have gone beyond local and national scales. Factors such as trust between organizations and shared need have been key to sustaining alliances, although obstacles persist related to the lack of resources, political changes, and the closure of spaces for civil society participation.

Finally, the group stressed that a strategic next step is to move towards transnational litigation based on territorial monitoring systems, satellite information, and regional repositories that document rights violations. They called for strengthening regional coordination and collective work between Indigenous organizations, legal specialists, and allied organizations to jointly confront the cross-border dynamics of criminality that affect Amazonia.

Figure 26. Preparation of the group stand and presentation of the experiences

Stand 10. IUCN Small Grants Facility
 Member: Cecilia Saenz

Cecilia presented the experience of an IUCN small grants mechanism in Central and South America, aimed at strengthening Indigenous territorial processes from a rights-based and environmental justice approach. The mechanism was structured around three main strategic lines: strengthening territorial management and governance, protection of defenders, and communication for advocacy and economic empowerment. The mechanism financed 11 projects in Ecuador, Peru, and Honduras, selected through a broad call coupled with an evaluation process that incorporated criteria of gender equity and youth participation. Fifty-

eight Indigenous organizations and 19 Peoples or nationalities participated, directly benefiting more than a thousand people, with a high participation of women.

A central factor was that resources reached Indigenous organizations directly. This made it possible to strengthen their administrative, financial, and technical capacities, as well as their autonomy to define priorities and carry out actions aligned with their specific territorial needs. She stressed that this approach favored organizational strengthening and local ownership of the projects.

Among the main results are the creation of territorial governance tools and protection mechanisms for defenders, the development of communication strategies for advocacy, and implementation of multiple capacity-building workshops. Several organizations even managed to consolidate their own management processes and expand their territorial articulation networks.

Various challenges faced include sustainability and scalability of the mechanism, administrative and financial requirements, the limited project execution time, and the selection criteria required to access the funds. However, she stressed that several organizations managed to use this experience to strengthen their institutional capacities and subsequently access new financing and partnerships.

Next steps proposed included a search for new resources to replicate the mechanism in other countries and territories, expand strategic lines of work, strengthen exchanges and networks between Indigenous organizations, and systematize learning through communication tools and dissemination of experiences.

Questions and answers: Hugo asked about the criteria for selecting the small grants mechanism. Cecilia explained that the mechanism was implemented directly in the territory and that IUCN mainly assumed administrative and financial oversight, while the Indigenous organizations themselves led mobilization and execution of activities together with their bases and local allies.

Territorial organizations were prioritized in the selection criteria, although other organizations were also incorporated as long as they met the requirements of due diligence and administrative and financial capacities. The fundamental criterion was to ensure that resources effectively reached Indigenous territories and communities. In some cases, work was done through partner organizations that met the administrative requirements needed to channel the funds, while ensuring that implementation would be under local community control.

Johanna highlighted the protection line for defenders and asked for concrete examples of funded initiatives related to territorial self-defense and community protection. Cecilia explained that one experience supported a project of itinerant schools promoted by a regional Indigenous organization that sought to bring information on Indigenous rights directly to communities and territories. The project was based on the recognition that many communities do not have in-depth knowledge of existing rights frameworks, so the itinerant schools combined legal training processes with construction of territorial self-defense protocols

developed from their own community knowledge and practices. These protocols incorporated ancestral knowledge, cultural practices, and their own forms of territorial surveillance and protection. An Ecuadorian case with the Cofán people also was cited, which aimed at building a territorial agenda and community defense protocols against external threats, in a context where state responses were insufficient.

Figure 27. Preparation of the stand and presentation of the experience

2. Reflections to close the day

Johanna, the thematic leader, emphasized that taken together, the cases show that Indigenous Peoples and allied organizations are promoting increasingly complex processes of territorial governance, defense of rights, and regional articulation. Although the contexts are different, there is a common trend towards consolidation of autonomies and their own governance mechanisms, strengthening of Indigenous leadership, construction of regional networks, and articulation between knowledge, political advocacy, and territorial protection.

At the same time, the cases show that these processes need sustainability, collective protection, and greater coordination capacities to confront increasingly transnational and structural threats. From the experiences presented, common elements were identified:

- The centrality of territory and the defense of rights: A cross-cutting element is that territory appears as the articulating axis of the political, organizational, and legal

strategies of Indigenous Peoples. From construction of Indigenous autonomies in Bolivia, the Amazonian regional alliances, the strategies against illegal mining, or the mechanisms of small donations, the territory is understood not only as a physical space, but as the basis of collective life and identity. There is a tendency to combine legal, organizational, political, and communication strategies to sustain territorial defense, going beyond exclusively legal or technical approaches.

- Organizational strengthening and capacity building: There is still a need to strengthen Indigenous organizations through training, leadership, and technical support processes. The case on strengthening Indigenous Peoples Organizations with a gender and youth focus particularly shows how these processes seek to build long-term leadership and ensure generational continuity within organizations.
- The participation of women and youth: Most of the cases explicitly incorporate the need to strengthen political participation of Indigenous women and youth. The sustainability of territorial processes depends on expanding participation of new leaders and guaranteeing more equitable spaces within organizational structures.
- The importance of alliances and articulations: All cases show that alliances are essential to face complex problems on a regional scale. Articulations are necessary at different levels, between Indigenous Peoples, between Indigenous organizations and civil society, between organizations from different countries, and between regional networks and international bodies.
- The scales of incidence: From the local to the international, cases reflect a growing articulation between local territorial actions and international advocacy. This shows an expansion of Indigenous strategies towards multiple scales of governance, where the local and the global appear increasingly connected.

Figure 28. Final Reflections in plenary

Confraternization and Personal Connections to the Amazon.

As a closing activity for the day, participants were invited to bring an object or create a drawing that symbolized their relationship with the Amazon. This exercise provided a meaningful opportunity for personal reflection and exchange, fostering a more informal and human-centered atmosphere among the group. Through the stories shared, participants revealed not only the professional pathways that connect them to the region but also the personal experiences, memories, values, and aspirations that shape their engagement with Amazonia.

The exercise highlighted the diversity of perspectives present in the room and underscored the deep emotional, cultural, and spiritual significance that the Amazon holds for many participants. Several contributions illustrated how professional commitments are often intertwined with personal identities, family histories, and lived experiences.

By creating space for these narratives, the session strengthened mutual understanding, built trust among participants, and reinforced a shared sense of responsibility toward the future of the region. The activity also revealed the richness and complexity of participants' connections to the Amazon. While some shared stories rooted in their professional trajectories, others reflected on childhood memories, ancestral ties, transformative field experiences, or the inspiration they draw from the region's peoples, cultures, and ecosystems. These exchanges highlighted that engagement with Amazonia extends well beyond institutional roles, reflecting enduring personal bonds and long-term commitments.

Figure 29. Final reflections in plenary and closing of the day

DAY 4. SHARED COMMITMENTS AND PARTNERSHIPS FOR NEXT STEPS

The opening activity on Day 4 began with an "imaginary journey to the Amazon", a dynamic in which each participant shared a place or personal connection with the Amazon, evidencing the diversity of affective, political, and cultural ties with the region. Places mentioned included the Serranía de Chiribiquete and the Salto del Diablo in Colombia, highlighted by their geographical majesty and the interconnection between the Andes and Amazon; the Azu Reserve in Putumayo, created by women to protect the knowledge of grandmothers of fifteen Indigenous Peoples; the Pastaza River in Ecuador, noted for the coexistence of multiple Indigenous nationalities and the richness of their cultural practices; sacred territories and communities in Bolivia such as Loma Santa (Narhal), the Moxeño territory of San José de Cabito, and the Chimán community of the Chimti River, associated with memories of refuge, spirituality, and coexistence with fauna; various Amazonian rivers in Peru and Brazil such as the Ampillangu, the Chicú, the Panqui and the Caquetá, which connect communities, migration memories, and daily practices; as well as emblematic and urban spaces such as Manaus and Xapurí, Acre in Brazil, linked to experiences of encounter, gastronomy, and community life. Indigenous territories such as the Sibundoy Valley in Colombia were also mentioned for their ritual and syncretic value, the upper Amazon of Ecuador for its biodiversity and life experiences, and the Yasuni National Park as a symbol of megadiversity and the presence of Peoples in voluntary isolation. Together, this dynamic made it possible to make the Amazon visible not only as a geographical space, but a living territory crossed by memories, affections, political struggles, spiritualities, and trajectories of mobility that overflow national borders.

After the opening activity, the facilitator presented the agenda of the closing workshop day, which included a space for collective reflection on the "fair" held the day before, attention to pending questions from the group, a dialogue on the POC project, discussion of the next steps of both project and participants, and a final evaluation.

1. Collective reflections on the Fair of Experiences

1.1. Cross-border efforts against illegalities

During the collective dialogue space, Antonio shared a contribution focused on the experience of Indigenous governments of the Amazonian macro-territory in Colombia in the face of illegal mining and mercury pollution. He explained that, after a tutela action filed approximately five or six years ago, Judgment T-106 was issued, ruling that four plaintiff Indigenous governments and 27 state institutions were linked, including ministries and authorities of Caquetá and Amazonia. The Court established 32 orders or "remedies" that must be implemented through inter-institutional coordination mechanisms, and especially highlighted the recognition of the "books"—Blue Book, Green Book, and the root book—as Indigenous knowledge systems that should guide the implementation of the judgment.

He also emphasized that the Amazonian macro-territory transcends Colombia's national borders and includes territories in Brazil and Venezuela, so the impacts of illegal mining and mercury must be addressed from a larger basin perspective and with cross-border articulation. He maintained that the ruling politically and legally strengthens the regional work promoted by the different Amazonian alliances.

Juana agreed that the experience of coordinating the macro-territory and Judgment T-106 constitute a key reference to guide regional alliances against illegal mining. She indicated a next line of work will be precisely to support compliance with the "remedies" established by the Court. She also stressed that the Colombian experience represents an important reference for articulation processes that are being strengthened in Peru and other Amazonian countries. She highlighted the progress made in areas of regional advocacy, particularly in the framework of ACTO and the Working Group on Cross-Border Illicit Acts and Illegal Economies, where references to illegal gold mining and mercury and gold traceability were incorporated into the Bogotá Declaration. However, she cautioned against the institutional limitations of ACTO, given its dependence on the political will of States and the slow pace of civil society input. In view of this, a multilevel advocacy strategy is being promoted together with advisors and regional actors.

As next steps, Juana pointed out the need to form an interdisciplinary legal group, prioritize critical areas, and advance in joint control, traceability, and bioremediation mechanisms. She warned about the growing role of organized crime groups linked to illegal mining, indicating that the speed and adaptation of these groups is not the same as the speed and adaptation of the law, which represents one of the main challenges for regional control strategies.

In this context, Johanna raised the need to deepen the discussion on how to act against articulation between illegal mining and armed groups or organized crime structures. She pointed out that these actors are usually heavily armed and that their presence constitutes a permanent threat to communities and territories, making it necessary to think about specific strategies for protection and action.

Andrea complemented this reflection by pointing out that much of the financing that was previously concentrated in drug trafficking has shifted to illegal mining due to its high profitability. This requires coordinated responses among Amazonian countries and explained that an important part of the current work consists of articulating environmental prosecutors' offices, institutions in charge of controlling money laundering, and other state entities linked to the fight against illicit economies. Illegal mining should be understood as part of a broader network of organized crime and mentioned international efforts aimed at tracking money and money laundering chains from illegal activities.

Maria pointed out that the Moore Foundation has supported initiatives related to tax transfers and asset transparency as part of a broader agenda aimed at confronting organized crime and strengthening financial control mechanisms.

Finally, in response to a comment by Pilar on the traceability of mercury, Juana explained that due to its serious environmental impacts and the health of the riverside populations, the challenge is to trace the entire chain of mercury circulation – from its entry into the territories

to the international circuits—. While there are advances in monitoring and bioremediation, gaps persist in the routes of trade, distribution, and institutional control of mercury in countries such as Peru and Colombia.

Figure 30. Final reflections in plenary and closing of the day

1.2. Group reflections

Tita proposed a brief exercise in which participants reorganized themselves into the working groups of the previous day to reflect on experiences presented, focusing on how they arrived at the topic presented and how they prepared their presentations. She stressed that although at the beginning, groups wanted to cover many topics, the process allowed them to focus and prioritize ideas, achieving clearer presentations despite limited time. She then invited them to review the works again with "fresh eyes", highlighting the diversity of experiences and knowledge present in the workshop.

Antonio's group pointed out that their presentation arose from recurring discussions since the beginning of the workshop, which led them to explain more deeply the approach of the macro-territory as a central axis. They explained that the guiding questions helped to prioritize and synthesize the information, organizing the presentation in cultural, political, and legal dimensions.

Wânia's group commented that they started from a case that they initially considered small, but that when contextualized it, showed greater complexity and impact on Indigenous communities. They highlighted the articulation with the case of the Munduruku people and the importance of making displacements, territorial affectations, and Indigenous leaders visible in judicial processes.

Silvana said that reviewing the cases again gave her hope by recognizing progress in different countries in the region, strengthening the sense of brotherhood and the idea that collective processes allow territorial struggles to be sustained.

Leonardo observed a strong complementarity between the topics presented, highlighting the rapprochement between environmental, legal, and Indigenous agendas. However, he warned that Indigenous issues still have little presence in government agendas, which shows the need to strengthen alliances and articulations.

Luisa highlighted the potential of building an Amazonian regional narrative that connects the different experiences shared, including legal advances, challenges, and the role of Indigenous Peoples and civil society. She proposed systematizing this learning through visual tools and regional infographics.

Walter said that the space generated positive expectations for him and that he valued the learning and alliances built, although he pointed out that important challenges remain, especially in Peru. He stressed the need to strengthen regional coordination and expand Indigenous participation in these processes.

Pilar reflected on the dynamic nature of regional processes, marked by legal, institutional, and political changes. She stressed the importance of positioning the relationship between conservation, politics, and Indigenous territories in different sectors through information and awareness.

Finally, Antonio stressed that in all the presentations the Indigenous Peoples naturally appeared as central actors. He pointed out the importance of strengthening the articulation between Indigenous Peoples from different countries and of maintaining the support of international cooperation and other allies to consolidate the network promoted by the workshop.

2. Collective learning: What did we bring, what did we learn and what did we take away from the workshop?

The facilitator indicated that a half-hour exercise would be carried out in which each participant had to first reflect individually on what they learned and take away from the workshop, and then share it in groups. To organize the activity, she randomly assigned numbers to the participants to form the groups.

Group 1 (Vanessa, Leonardo, Silvana, Antonio):

The group highlighted the importance of cross-border articulation in the face of threats such as illegal mining and other illicit economies, as well as the value of alliances between Indigenous Peoples, civil society, and environmental actors.

Silvana underscored the regional interest in experiences such as the Indigenous Territorial Entities in Colombia and the need to exchange tools, methodologies, and lessons learned on governance, territorial management, and legal strengthening, especially for Indigenous

youth. She also emphasized the importance of continuing to share jurisprudence, innovative strategies, and comparative experiences to strengthen collective rights and the protection of the Amazon.

Finally, they highlighted experiences of Indigenous governance and prior consultation in countries such as Colombia, Bolivia, and Peru, identifying both progress and limitations in their implementation. The group agreed that governance was a cross-cutting axis of the workshop, along with the need to strengthen work with women and youth, promote regional exchanges, and consolidate collective responses to common problems.

Group 2 (Juan David, Maria, Karen, Luisa, Juana):

This group identified the comparative analysis between the processes of Indigenous autonomy in Bolivia and the Indigenous Territorial Entities in Colombia, highlighting similarities, common challenges, and useful lessons to strengthen regional strategies.

Karen and Juana highlighted the importance of understanding the law as a tool at the service of territorial struggles and not as an end in itself, as well as deepening legal pluralism, territorial co-management, and prior consultation. They also underscored the value of networks, coalitions, and collective intelligence to sustain regional advocacy processes.

The group also emphasized the need to strengthen the regional Intercultural Pact, maintain territorial work as the basis for political advocacy, and promote long-term cooperation and financing processes, in accordance with the complexity of structural changes in the Amazon.

Group 3 (Nadia, Catalina, Darío, Walter, Carolina, Johanna, Yulissa):

The group highlighted the different forms of Indigenous governance present in Bolivia, Colombia, Peru, and Brazil, recognizing differentiated advances according to the political and regulatory contexts of each country.

Johanna and Yulissa highlighted the value of the workshop's participatory methodologies, especially the Fair of Experiences. They also noted the importance of cross-border alliances and the exchange of practical tools to address problems such as illegal mining and mercury pollution.

The group also identified a transformation in conservation approaches, which are increasingly articulated with Indigenous rights and territories. Carolina emphasized the need to maintain the dialogues initiated in the workshop, share learnings, and build regional strategies based on major legal and territorial milestones.

Group 4 (Pilar, Rafael, Lawrence, Alex, Hugo):

This group highlighted the knowledge of regional experiences of Indigenous territorial governance linked to conservation, highlighting its usefulness to anticipate challenges and strengthen national processes.

Pilar, Hugo and Rafael stressed the importance of building public policies together with Indigenous Peoples, as well as articulating territorial protection, conservation, and Indigenous rights from comprehensive approaches. They also pointed out the need to

strengthen protection mechanisms for defenders and promote regional exchanges on prior consultation, governance, and conflict management.

They stressed that the experiences reviewed show that it is possible to overcome the vision that conservation and Indigenous Peoples are in opposing corners, identifying multiple points of convergence and regional articulation.

Figure 31. Workshop participants during plenary discussion

Closing reflection by the thematic leader:

Johanna presented the general conclusions of the group activity, highlighting that workshop presentations and dialogues made it possible to identify multiple common elements between shared experiences. She pointed out that the Amazon should be understood as a region of great biological and cultural diversity, but also marked by shared structural challenges and threats.

In addition, she underscored the importance of strengthening connections and collaboration between actors to consolidate existing advances and to promote a regional and comprehensive vision of the Amazon that transcends national borders and that articulates rights, conservation, and territory. This regional articulation is key to sustaining processes of change and strengthening innovative strategies.

She also highlighted the advances in legal frameworks and in the use of the law as a tool for territorial and environmental protection, recognizing differentiated experiences between countries and pointing to the case of Bolivia as an important reference for learning. Finally, she emphasized the need to take advantage of the complementarity between the different

cases and processes presented, identifying common axes such as governance, political changes, and shared threats to strengthen regional collaborative work.

Figure 32. Closing reflection by the thematic leader

3. Weaving a common agenda for the Amazon

Vanessa presented the next steps of the *Power of Connections* project, noting that a detailed report of the workshop will be prepared and shared with participants for validation before publication. She indicated that later, shorter dissemination products will be developed – such as an executive summary and graphic materials – to share the learnings of the meeting, in addition to keeping the WhatsApp group active as a permanent space for exchange between participants from different countries and workshops.

Based on this, Jon proposed opening an autonomous space for conversation among the participants to collectively define how to give continuity to the bonds built during the workshop. The discussion made it possible to identify common interests, initial commitments, and possible lines of joint work.

The first person to speak, Juana, raised the need to move towards a collective construction of regional thought and reflection on legal pluralism and Indigenous rights in the Amazon. She proposed preparing a joint text that collects learnings, tensions, and comparative experiences between countries, pointing out that this effort should be developed "by many hands" and projected as a long-term process. In the same vein, Luisa stressed the importance of not only compiling cases, but also analyzing how Indigenous Peoples have transformed and influenced the sources of law from their own knowledge systems. As an example, she mentioned the idea of an "indigenization of law," understood as processes through which territorial struggles and Indigenous knowledge reconfigure legal frameworks and protection mechanisms.

Silvana proposed to start with concrete and achievable actions in the short term to prevent dilution of workshop momentum. She suggested organizing the information by common countries and thematic lines, as well as building a shared repository of judgments, decrees, jurisprudence, and relevant experiences that can serve as a tool for regional consultation. She also proposed defining a small work plan with short, medium, and long-term goals, including a virtual follow-up meeting in about a month. Antonio agreed with this continuity concern and emphasized the need for what was discussed not to remain only in the space of the workshop, but to have endurance in the territories and organizational processes. He compared the meeting to a "small COP", highlighting that it facilitated discussion of common problems and thinking on practical tools for regional coordination. In addition, he pointed out that together with participants from Bolivia and Peru, they will seek to take these discussions to territorial coordination spaces in the Amazon.

Nadia proposed strengthening an Amazonian network of Indigenous lawyers and proposed as a future initiative the creation of a digital repository to preserve evidence on crimes and affectations in the territories, with useful standards for judicial and international processes. Andrea complemented this idea by pointing out that there are already exchanges of information between Indigenous organizations and legal actors in Colombia, Peru, and Brazil, especially around problems related to illegal mining and environmental crimes.

The discussion also highlighted the need to maintain clear objectives and a manageable scope for a collective space. Leonardo noted that the group could focus primarily on the exchange of useful information for territorial defense, sharing jurisprudence, protocols, and practical experiences from different countries. He mentioned as an example Bolivia's progress in legal pluralism and prior consultation, where there are guidelines developed by the Constitutional Court and other institutions to guide interpretation of Indigenous and environmental rights.

Hugo recalled previous experiences of regional environmental law networks that managed to sustain themselves for years through virtual exchanges, collective publications, and periodically updating spaces, pointing out that continuity depends more on clear objectives and concrete commitments than on large organizational structures.

The need to maintain a broad and interdisciplinary approach also emerged. Catalina warned that the space should not be reduced only to legal discussions, since one of the main learnings of the workshop was precisely the connection between conservation, Indigenous territorial management, and collective rights. In response, Luisa proposed working from a logic of

intersection between Indigenous rights, conservation, climate change, youth and gender, pointing out that Indigenous territories managed with autonomy represent some of the spaces with the lowest levels of deforestation and constitute fundamental actors for Amazonian climate stability.

Pilar also introduced a critical reflection on the tensions between different regulatory frameworks in the region. She noted that while some environmental laws promote conservation, many agrarian laws continue to incentivize expansion of the agricultural frontier and deforestation, particularly in the Amazon. This observation opened a discussion on the coexistence of contradictory legal and development models.

Finally, Juana synthesized several of the consensuses reached, proposing to organize future work around three initial lines:

- 1) Share information through a common repository.
- 2) Activate solidarity and support mechanisms in the face of urgent situations in the territory.
- 3) Gradually advance in collective exercises of systematization and regional reflection.

The participants agreed that the main value of the workshop was the building of connections between diverse experiences, strengthening shared learning, and opening a space of trust to continue collaborating in the face of the common challenges facing the Amazon.

Figure 33. Plenary discussion on commitments and next steps

4. Closing Activity and Final Reflections

Tita invited the participants to take a tour in pairs of the materials and products made during the four days of the workshop to collectively revisit the experience and prepare for a final reflection of key learnings. Subsequently, Vanessa requested to complete the evaluation of the workshop, which was shared through the WhatsApp group in different languages.

Figure 34. Participants during the tour activity

During the closing, Hugo pointed out that although the workshop prioritized positive experiences and progress, more in-depth discussions on the "white elephants" or structural challenges that these processes go through were still pending. Leonardo agreed on the need to deepen the relationship between Indigenous rights and defense of the Amazon, noting that this connection became clearer as shared experiences progressed.

In the same vein, Mafer stressed the importance of addressing uncomfortable conversations related to illegal mining, political changes, and the financial sustainability of autonomous strategies, noting that these discussions generate a "productive distress" necessary to anticipate future scenarios and strengthen collective responses.

Figure 35. Participants during the tour activity

In the final reflections, Karen highlighted the importance of strengthening relations between civil society and Indigenous Peoples, promoting spaces that move "from protest to proposal" as Walter declared, and recognizing the value of biocultural diversity and the alliances built during the workshop.

Finally, Tita invited the group to reflect on the connections generated throughout the process and on the innovative ideas or practices that each participant took with them. The workshop concluded with a collective symbolic gesture of closure and political and affective affirmation. All participants raised their voices together three times:

"Amazonia lives!"

" Amazonia lives!"

"Amazonia lives!"

This closing expressed the shared commitment to the defense of the Amazon - its territories and Indigenous Peoples - as well as the collective strength built during the days of work.

Figure 36. Participants during the closing activity of the workshop

About the project “The Power of Connections”

The "Power of Connections" project is led by the Tropical Conservation and Development Program (TCD) of the Center for Latin American Studies at the University of Florida (UF), in partnership with the Gordon and Betty Moore Foundation. "Harvesting lessons and strengthening coalitions for the conservation of the Amazon" is at the heart of this project, which seeks to connect people and collaboratively develop pathways for the lasting conservation of the Pan-Amazon. This project is funded by the Gordon and Betty Moore Foundation through GBMF13270 grants.

About TCD

The mission of the Tropical Conservation and Development Program (TCD) is to connect theory and practice to promote biodiversity conservation, sustainable use of natural resources, and human well-being in the tropics and beyond. TCD is a research and training program of the University of Florida's Center for Latin American Studies, with 10 tenured faculty and approximately 100 affiliated faculty across campus. The program has a long history of collaboration with partner organizations in the Amazon and support networks of conservation professionals committed to sustainable development.

About the Moore Foundation

The Gordon and Betty Moore Foundation promotes scientific discovery, environmental conservation, and the special character of the San Francisco Bay Area. Since 2001, its Andes-Amazon Initiative has helped conserve more than 400 million hectares in the Amazon. By 2031, the initiative aims to ensure that 70% of the Amazon biome (forest cover) and the freshwater ecosystems that support it are under effective management and conservation. Visit Moore.org and follow [@MooreFound](https://twitter.com/MooreFound) for more information.

APPENDIX

A. Complete and detailed workshop agenda

Workshop Goal

This workshop aims to collectively analyze innovative legal instruments and strategies for strengthening Indigenous Peoples’ rights protection, self-determination, and the development of inclusive policies in the Amazon. Participants will share successful cases and approaches while identifying meaningful lessons and practical insights with implications for Amazon conservation.

Workshop thematic objectives

- Assess positive impacts that governance instruments (rules, laws, policies, strategies) have had on the protection of life, territories, and rights in the Amazon.
- Reflect on the effectiveness of legal frameworks in promoting the design and implementation of policies focused on protecting the rights of Indigenous Peoples in the Amazon.
- Share innovative strategies that have proven effective in enabling Indigenous agency for self-determination in the Amazon.
- Collectively outline next steps that can support the strengthening of coalitions in favor of Indigenous rights, effective governance, and Amazon conservation.

Time	Session	Objectives	Activity	Details
Monday night, January 26 – AFTER DINNER				
19:30	After dinner, Opening and Welcome	Create a welcoming environment and begin to get to know each other	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Welcome 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Opener: ● Host’s Welcome CIPRI – 10 min ● Welcome words from Indigenous Ecuadorian representative – Marilyn from CONFENIAE (10 Min) ● UF/Moore: Maria DiGiano and Karen (10 min) ● Karen introduces Johanna—Brief contextualization of the collaborative workshop organization process.

				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Team lead, Johanna, presents a general vision of the agenda for 3 days (15 min.) ● Informed Consent for pictures and audios ● Presentation of the facilitators: Tita Alvira and Jon Dain
20:00-21:30	Introductions		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Map and Participants introductions 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Name/Location on map (map on the wall) <p>Participants mark the name/location on the map of the Amazon basin using sticky notes (where you live, work)</p>
Day 1 – Tuesday, January 27, 2026 Guidelines and Trust Building Setting the stage: Legal strategies and governance instruments for conservation				
8:00	POC: Project overview	Alignment between participants	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Agenda/Objectives /Logistics ● Expectations & Norms (Acuerdo de convivencia) 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● OPENER–Welcome to the new participants who were not on Monday night ● Workshop Goals, agenda, logistics, etc. (Tita-10 min.) ** Guiding principles ● Small groups discuss expectations and present out (30 min) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Expectations presented (summary here from the virtual pre-workshop meeting); additional expectations discussed or included by those who did not attend the virtual meeting. ● Plenary discussion of Normas de Convivencia (15 min) **Guiding principles: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Bring something useful (method, approach, case, lesson learned) ● Come out with something useful (method, approach, case, lesson learned) ● Make a new connection that you keep
10:00	Break			
10:00	Definition of terms:	Define terms/concepts, Collective understanding to set a		<i>Collective understanding sets a foundation for deeper discussions</i> <p>Johanna presents how we are framing this workshop-using flipchart innovative strategies (5 mins)</p>

		foundation for deeper discussions		<p>1. Interactions between Indigenous rights and conservation</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> How do you understand the relationship between conservation and Indigenous rights in your territory, region, country, and area of work? <i>STEPS: 1) Individual, 2) small groups, 3) plenary</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Individual writing/reflection (10 min) Small groups (4-5 people) (Mixed groups) Discuss and record in flipcharts (30 min) Sharing in plenary by groups - Each group 5 mins (25 mins) <p>2. Innovative strategies for effective rights protection and governance (55) (11:10-12:05)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> When you hear the term “innovative strategies, what comes to mind from your experience or work? <i>STEPS: 1) small groups, 2) plenary</i> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> Small groups (4-5 people) (5 groups by country) Discuss and record in flipcharts (30 min) Sharing in plenary by groups- Each group 5 mins (25 mins) <p>3. Indigenous self-determination and territorial self-governance (12:05-12:30)</p> <p>There is a difference between Indigenous self-determination and territorial self-governance. What is it? Request examples from the group. ~25 min <i>STEPS: Facilitated discussion in plenary, requesting examples.</i></p>
12:30 - 14:15		Lunch		
14:15			Energizer	
14:30	Reflections		Participants share opinions	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Review: Now that the topics are defined and understood:

				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ What do each of you bring to this workshop that can benefit others?
15:00	Indigenous Peoples' rights in National frameworks	*Identify and compare: Identify examples of how IPR rights are successfully recognized in the national framework (common and, different elements)	Group exercise by country	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Instructions, objective of the exercise (5 mins) ● Group discussions by country 6 groups (COL 5 pax, BR 6 pax, BOL 3 pax, EC 3 pax + JE, PE 4 pax, GY 1 pax) (30 mins) with guiding questions. Each group organizes responses in flipcharts with post its for comparative analysis.
15:35 Break				
15:55	Indigenous Peoples' rights in National frameworks	cont	cont	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Each group presents (5 mins x 6 groups = 30 mins), ask for active listening and similarities and differences ● Guided discussion-Analysis of similarities and differences and political implications (30 mins)
16:55	Introduce the Feria	Feria de Experiencias		<p>Introduce the feria:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● What specific examples of innovative strategies have translated into effective protection of life, territories, and rights in the Amazon that you want to share in the feria? that you think others here should know about? <p>STEPS: Brainstorm strategies that come to mind.</p>
17:45-18:00	Conclusion		Discussion in plenary	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● What we did today: review of the day's activities and objectives ● Conclusions? ● Tomorrow's agenda ● Thank you to the translators, notetakers, CIPRI, Vanessa, Fabian and others?

18:00	Power of connections	Getting to know each other personal and professional	Find 1-2 people to talk to - possible connections	
19:00	Dinner			
Day 2 – Wednesday, January 28, 2026				
Sharing Innovative strategies that have translated into effective protection of life, territories, and rights in the Amazon				
8:00	Opening		Looking back/Looking forward	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Opener-Around our connections table, take a look at it, something new? What new connections have emerged and in what themes? • What are you grateful for? What makes you smile this month? • Brief Review of Day I and Introduction to Day II Agenda
8:30	Feria de Experiencias		Prepare for “Feria de Experiencias Innovadoras y Replicables”	Preparation for stands Each stand will have a template on how to organize the information
10:00	Break			
10:15 (1.45 hour)	Feria cont.	cont.	Feria de Experiencias Innovadoras y Replicables	Fair begins Participants have a list to record what they are learning
12:30	Lunch			
13:45			Energizer	Energizer
14:00 (1.5 hour)	Feria cont.	cont		
15:30	Break			
15:45		cont.	Feria de Experiencias	
16:45-17:00	Conclusion		Discussion in plenary	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What we did today: review of the day's activities and objectives • Conclusions?

				<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Tomorrow's agenda • Thank you to the translators, notetakers, CIPRI, Vanessa, and others? • Invite to the Intercultural Night
17:15	Power of connections	Chance to network	Find 1-2 people to talk to - possible connections	
18:15	Break			
19:00	Dinner			
EVENING CONFRATERNIZACION – Noche Intercultural - Fire Pit				
Day 2 – Thursday, January 29, 2026 Pulling it all together: Alliances and the road ahead				
8:00	Opening		Looking back/Looking forward	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Opener: "Think of a place in the Amazon that you'd love to show people if you could." • Brief review of Day II and introduction to Day III agenda
9:00	Discussion and reflection Feria de Experiencias			<p>Small group discussion</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What have we learned from these experiences? <p>Plenary report out and discussion</p>
10:30	Break			
11:00	Pulling it all together			<p>What are you taking away from this workshop?</p> <p>In smalls groups, discuss using guiding questions:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What innovative idea did you bring? • What new idea will you take home and apply? • Who did you connect with? Will you follow up with? <p>In plenary:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • X things you liked about the workshop? • What changes would have made the workshop better?
12:30	Lunch			

13:30	Discussion	Power of connections (1 HOUR)		Vanessa presents POC products (report, executive analysis, digital report, etc.) In plenary, participants collectively decide what products they want to develop or what futures activities they want to carry on.
15:30 Break				
16:00	Evaluation			<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ● Gallery walk: all flipcharts created are hold in the walls. Tita asks participants to visit them, in pairs, to recognize the work developed through these workshop's days. ● Formal evaluation: Vanessa asks participants to complete an online evaluation form.
17:00	Wrap-up, conclusions and closure	Facilitated synthesis, Closing circle	Closing and conclusions	Facilitated synthesis, Closing circle Final thoughts/closure
18:00 Dinner				